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Use case characterization, KPIs and preferred suitable frequency ranges for future 5G systems between 6 GHz and 100 GHz

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Abstract

In this deliverable use cases and KPIs of interest for mmMAGIC are characterized. Eight use cases suitable for 5G systems operating in the range 6-100GHz are identified in terms of requirements. In particular, the following use cases are analyzed: Media on demand; Cloud services; Dense urban society with distributed crowds; Smart offices; Immersive 5G early experience in targeting hot spots; 50+Mbps everywhere; Moving hot spots; Tactile internet/video augmented robotic control and remote-robot manipulation surgery. For each of the use cases, the more critical KPIs are identified and the gap from the current technology is also described.

An analysis of frequency ranges for future 5G systems between 6 GHz and 100 GHz is reported. A frequency assessment study is conducted in order to compare the frequency ranges for the suitability of delivering key KPIs.

Keywords

5G system, use cases, KPI, requirements, mm-wave, spectrum

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Executive summary

The overall objective of the mmMAGIC project is to design and develop a concept for a mobile radio access technology (RAT) operating in the frequency range 6-100GHz that is expected to be an integral part of the 5G multi-RAT ecosystem.

This deliverable (D1.1), named “Use cases characterization, KPIs and preferred suitable frequency ranges for future 5G systems between 6GHz and 100GHz”, summarizes the results of use cases, KPIs and spectrum investigations and shall be used as reference by the other WPs.

In particular, this deliverable covers the study of the following objectives included in the work package 1 of mmMAGIC (Technology ecosystem enablers and visualization):

1. The state of the art with respect to 5G use cases and requirements relevant for mmMAGIC
2. The basic terminology and definitions that will be used in mmMAGIC
3. The definition of families of use cases and a list of use cases that are foreseen to be interesting within the scope of mmMAGIC.
4. An initial analysis of the usage of mobile cellular services offered in the frequencies in the range of 6-100GHz
5. An indication of the technology readiness in the frequency range considered
6. A frequency assessment study on the available bandwidths to compare the frequency ranges for the suitability of delivering key KPIs.

This is the first WP1 deliverable describing use cases of interest and available frequencies in the range of 6-100GHz to be used as baseline for the mmMAGIC project. Eight use cases of interest are considered, and the fundamental KPIs and the gap from current technology are described.

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of the mmMAGIC project is to design and develop a concept for a mobile radio access technology (RAT) operating in the frequency range 6-100GHz that is expected to be an integral part of the 5G multi-RAT ecosystem. Amongst the wide range of 5G requirements, the focus of the mmMAGIC project is on ultra-dense deployments and ultra-high capacity services for mobile devices which are expected to drive the 5G requirements for massive increase in capacity and data-rates.

The mmMAGIC project is structured in 6 different work packages (WPs), five of technical nature and one for management and dissemination. The technical work packages contents range from the definition of user needs and implications of regulatory constraints, via channel measurements and modelling, to research on system and radio interface concepts and solutions. The goal of the first work package, named “Technology and ecosystem enablers and visualization” is to provide use cases, deployment scenarios, key performance indicators (KPIs) and spectrum recommendations to the other work packages. In addition, the visualization activities as well as feasibility studies of the results produced by the other WPs are also included.

This deliverable, named “Use cases characterization, KPIs and preferred suitable frequency ranges for future 5G systems between 6GHz and 100GHz”, summarizes the results of use cases, KPIs and spectrum investigations and shall be used as reference by the other WPs. As also mentioned on the deliverable title, the frequencies investigated for extremely high capacity mobile broadband services in the scope of mmMAGIC are in the range of 6-100GHz.

The goal of this deliverable is twofold: to fix, by means of representative use cases, KPIs of interest for mmMAGIC and to select suitable frequency ranges to be investigated in order to develop a new mobile radio access technology, operating in wide contiguous bands considered above 6GHz.

This deliverable is organized in five sections. After the introduction, in the second section the state of the art and a short overview of the existing work on 5G are reported. In the third section a list of terminology and KPIs definitions is provided in order to have a common jargon across the work packages defined in the mmMAGIC project. The fourth section describes the use cases that will be studied in the mmMAGIC project, and for each of them it summarizes the related KPIs and the resulting requirements. In order to define a clear roadmap for the work to be conducted in the other WPs, the gap from the current technology is analysed as well. A table summarizes all the KPIs for the different use cases.

In the fifth section the advantages and the challenges of operating in frequencies above 6GHz (with respect to the current technology) to address the described KPIs are summarized.

In the sixth section, the analysis of the frequency bands in the range of 6-100GHz is provided. Three ranges, named low GHz (6-30GHz), mid GHz (30-50GHz) and high GHz (70-100GHz) are identified and separately studied. Although considered from the measurement and channel modelling point of view, the 51-70GHz frequency range has been excluded from this scope of mmMAGIC. A spectrum survey and the current ITU-R spectrum allocations for mobile services in the aforementioned frequency ranges are investigated, and an indication of the technology readiness in the considered frequency ranges is reported. Then the frequency assessment study conducted in mmMAGIC, based on KPIs (such as coverage, capacity, mobility and device complexity), is described.

Finally, the last section summarizes the work that has been done and provides some conclusions.

2 State of the Art

Several groups, consortia or projects have already started working on 5G, through either first definition of requirements, use cases and KPIs, or the specification of first technological enablers. Even though they usually consider 5G as a whole (i.e. they are not specific to cm-wave or mm-wave systems), they often include some specific requirements for systems employing higher bands, or at least mention the need for using these higher bands in order to meet some of the targeted objectives for 5G. This section provides a non-exhaustive overview of previous or ongoing works in projects and standardization groups related to use cases and requirements for 5G in bands above 6GHz.

- **NGMN:** The Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN) Alliance, founded by mobile operators and gathering vendors and research institutes, published in March 2015 a 5G White Paper [NGMN15]. This document provides key operator requirements for 5G and defines 8 families of use cases (each family including a few representative use cases). KPIs are derived from these use cases, setting performance targets for improving the user experience, enhancing the system performance and the network deployment, operation and management. This document is a landmark regarding 5G requirements and will serve as a main reference for the description of mmMAGIC use cases. This White Paper also highlights the need for new spectrum above 6GHz, with very wide bandwidth channel, to support deployments such as ultra-dense networks.
- **METIS:** The Mobile and wireless communications Enablers for the Twenty-twenty Information Society (METIS) project played an important role in starting the 5G discussion with the release of the Deliverable 1.1 in April 2013 [MET13-D11]. In this document the foreseen fundamental future challenges were identified and the overall technical goals that a 5G mobile and wireless system needs to fulfil were specified. Five different challenges, or scenarios, were identified together with twelve concrete test cases. The test cases are rather specific and were meant to facilitate the work around some selected research questions, but the solutions derived from them are foreseen to address the larger class of problems spanned by the scenarios. In the end of the project these scenarios, requirements and KPIs were revisited [MET15-D15]. Based on various industry perspectives it was concluded that the content remains highly valuable for the future evaluations of 5G technologies. In addition, one KPI and nine use cases were also identified as relevant due to technology trends and projections.

Most of the initiatives concern 5G in general, with some specific requirements or first indications on mm-wave or cm-wave systems. But some groups have already started focusing on 5G system in frequency ranges above 6GHz. Some other projects, even if not focusing on 5G, should be mentioned as well as other mm-wave initiatives for high-speed mobile applications. The most relevant groups or projects for mmMAGIC are:

- **MiWEBA:** The Millimetre-Wave Evolution for Backhaul and Access (MiWEBA) is a collaborative project in the FP7 framework with partners from Europe and Japan which aims to enable a capacity increase of mobile networks by 1000 times at reasonable cost and without loss of convenience to users. The basic concept is to overcome the current limitations by an integrated holistic approach using mm-wave technology, e.g. at 60GHz. The scenarios have been split into access and backhaul/fronthaul with three access sub-scenarios (indoor, outdoor, Multi-Technology Het Net scenarios) and two backhaul/fronthaul sub-scenarios covering point to point (P2P) and point to multipoint (PMP) architectures and mobile multi-hop relay node schemes [MiW13-D11]. To facilitate the development of technical solutions, six non exhaustive use cases have been defined: dense hotspots in a shopping mall, in an enterprise, in home and indoor environments, on a square, mobility in the city, and wireless and wired backhaul.
- **MiWaveS:** The Beyond 2020 heterogeneous wireless network with mm-wave small cell access and backhauling (MiWaveS) is a collaborative project in the FP7 framework

aiming at developing key technologies for the wireless access and backhaul for 5G, focusing on specific frequency ranges in the millimetre-wave spectrum (57-66GHz, 71-76GHz, 81-86GHz). The objective of the project is to provide high capacity mobile access, with peak data rates up to 2-5Gbps at the access (250Mbps at cell edge) and above 10Gbps of aggregate capacity for wireless backhaul [FFD+15]. Five distinct use cases have been defined: urban street-level outdoor mobile access and backhaul system, large public events and gatherings, indoor wireless networking and coverage from outdoor, rural detached small-cell zones and villages, hotspot in shopping mall.

- **IEEE 802.11ad / IEEE 802.11ay:** IEEE 802.11ad/WiGig is a new generation of Wi-Fi, moving from “traditional” Wi-Fi bands at 2.4GHz and 5GHz to the 60GHz band. This standard enables very high data rates (up to 7Gbps at the physical layer), thanks to the worldwide availability of wide contiguous bandwidth. The IEEE 802.11ad standard was published in December 2012, targeting applications like wireless display or wireless docking, and first products have emerged on the market over the past few years. This technology is supported by the strong Wi-Fi ecosystem, and can serve as a reference for indoor performance.

A new group has recently started in the IEEE 802.11 standardization body, to specify a second generation of WLAN at 60GHz, relying on the introduction of new techniques such as channel bonding or advanced Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) techniques to increase the data rates (at least to 20Gbps peak rates). This new group, labelled IEEE 802.11ay, will analyse licence-exempt bands above 45GHz including the current 60GHz band. Use cases have already been defined [IEEEENG60-15], and some of them are particularly relevant to mmMAGIC scope: Ultra Short Range communications (for example mass data download from a kiosk), 8K Ultra High Definition wireless transfer, augmented reality and virtual reality, Video on Demand system (crowded public spaces, inside transportation, etc.), mobile offloading, mobile fronthauling and wireless backhauling.

- **Regulatory groups:** The work has recently started in different regulatory groups, in order to pave the way for discussions on this topic at the World Radio Conference (WRC). Decisions will be taken, in WRC-19 (in 2019) but discussions already started during WRC-15 (November 2015) with the identification of a first set of frequency bands. In ITU-R, the Working Group WP5D has produced a report on “The technical feasibility of IMT in the bands above 6GHz” [ITU15]. Some national regulatory bodies have issued consultations. In the US, the FCC has released a Notice of Inquiry on “Use of Spectrum Bands above 24GHz for Mobile Radio Services” [FCC14]. In the UK, OFCOM delivered a report with identification of preliminary frequency ranges [OFCOM15]. The work will continue reviewing other options and refining this identification.

3 Terminology and KPIs Definition

In this section we provide a common terminology and KPI definitions used in this deliverable and through all mmMAGIC's use cases, which are solution agnostic. This terminology has been partly defined according to METIS project [MET13-D11] and partly in line with [NGMN15].

3.1 Terminology

Use case: A *general* account of a situation or course of actions that may occur in the future. It is described from end-user perspective and illustrates fundamental characteristics. In order to have a more concrete description, the challenges are described by means of representative use cases that contain a set of assumptions, constraints, and requirements.

Key Performance Indicator (KPI): A quantifiable measurement that reflects the critical success factors of a proposed solution; it reflects the goals captured by each use case. The KPIs are linked to the use case so as to link the proposed solutions with the usage driven test cases.

Requirement: Each use case is characterized by different needs in terms of KPIs. The quantified needs are called requirements in this deliverable. For example: If the KPI is delay the requirement could be 10ms.

Propagation environment: The propagation environment defines the medium between the access point (AP) and the User Equipment (UE).

In order to have for each use case a more specific characterization, the backhaul link between APs and the Base Station (BS) is not considered in the propagation environment definition (the backhaul link between APs and the backhaul BS is in fact always including outdoor and/or indoor/outdoor propagation no matter the use case considered).

cm-wave: is the notation for centimeter waves or bands, which are signals or radio waves with a wavelength from 1 to 10 cm equivalent to frequencies between 30GHz and 3GHz.

mm-wave: is the notation for millimeter waves or bands, which are signals or radio waves with a wavelength from 1 to 10 mm equivalent to frequencies between 300GHz and 30GHz.

3.2 KPIs Definition

User data rate UL/DL

This KPI refers to the user data rate (DR) at which the end user uploads (UL) or downloads (DL) a file at the application layer during a defined time period. It is provided in megabits per second (Mbps).

$$DR = \text{Object size (bits)} / (t_{end} - t_{start})$$

where t_{start} (second) is the time when the user initiates the download/upload of the object and t_{end} (second) is when the object is present somewhere else. Data rate at the application layer is lower than the one at the MAC layer, since additional overhead has to be considered from the higher layers. The requirement for the supported user data rate depends on each use case specification as for example the amount of supported users. Similar definitions are used in [MET13-D11] and [NGMN15] where MAC rate and application rate are respectively defined.

Connection density

The KPI refers to the average number of simultaneous active connections that can be supported by an operator in a given area, measured in connections per square kilometre

(connections/km²). One or several operators may be in the same area. This is an output of the system and it is used as a KPI to measure system performance similar to the one in [NGMN15]. For specific use cases, where the peak value of users assumes a fundamental role as KPI (for instance in case of crowded spaces), the peak connection density instead of the average value per square kilometre will be considered.

Traffic density

The traffic density is equal to the product of the connection density and the experienced user's data rate, measuring the amount of traffic exchanged from all the active connections in a given area. This definition does not capture user behaviour, thus the requirements in traffic density are overestimated. The measurement unit is in bits per second per square kilometre (bps/km²). In [NGMN15] similar KPI is used.

Mobility

The supported end user mobility is considered by this KPI, usually measured in kilometre per hour (km/h). When the user is just walking, mobility is defined as pedestrian; when the user is constantly at the same position, it is defined as static.

Reliability

In this project we define reliability exactly the same as in [MET13-D11], where it is an assessment criterion to describe the quality of a radio link connection for fulfilling a certain service level. Thus it is measured as the probability (%) that a certain amount of data to or from an end user device is successfully transmitted to another peer within a predefined time frame. Mathematically, the reliability (R) can be expressed as follows:

$$R = \Pr(L \leq D)$$

where L is the measured latency and D is the deadline characteristic of the test case.

Reliability is very critical for safety use cases that require super real time feedback. The reliability in today's wireless networks is dependent on the traffic load, on the coverage and on the service levels agreed with customers. Apart from enterprise business customers, in most cases only best effort is guaranteed.

Availability

This KPI is also defined as in [MET13-D11], where it corresponds to the satisfaction of the end user. It is correlated with reliability. Thus if reliability is maintained over a certain quality of experience (QoE) threshold, then also the availability is perceived as satisfactory, and the user experiences the service as available.

Mathematically, the availability (A) can be expressed as in function of the reliability as follows:

$$A = \Pr(R \geq QoE)$$

The availability is an assessment criterion to describe inside a coverage area the percentage (%) of where a service is provided to the end user with the user's requested QoE level. This KPI contributes to the optimization of the network layout. The availability in today's commercial mobile radio networks is primarily adapted to the coverage probability of a network (mostly related to 95%).

Latency

This is the latency perceived by the end user defined as the duration between the transmission of a small data packet from user terminal to the Layer 2 / Layer 3 interface of the 5G system destination. In some cases latency may also include the equivalent time needed to carry any response back, according to [NGMN]. The use cases where latency is a main challenge are the ones with respect to safety-relevant services (e.g. for V2V communications) that require fast

reactions of the involved parties as considered especially in the scenario of “Super real-time and reliable connections”. In [MET13-D11] it is defined as the RTT (round trip time) while in [NGMN15] it is called user plane latency.

4 Use Case families

In this section, we present the different families of use cases envisioned within the mmMAGIC project. For each family, representative use cases are described, with the relevant KPIs. These derived KPIs are crucial to drive the investigations within the project. They are compared with the performances of current mobile wireless system (LTE rel-12, IEEE 802.1ac/ad), to provide insights on the improvements to the state of the art by the new wireless systems. Eventually, the challenges of using mm-wave frequency ranges for these use cases are discussed. It should be noted that backhaul and fronthaul are implicitly included in the use cases description.

4.1 Broadband access in a dense area

In future mobile broadband systems, 1000-times higher data volume per area has been envisioned by year 2020 [MET13-D11]. End users expect to have high capacity seamless connections to wireless services also in densely populated areas where thousands of people per square kilometer live and/or work. Four use cases, representative of such a massively connected society, are described below.

4.1.1 Use Case 1: Media on demand

Description and Key Features

This use case captures the needs of end users to watch videos (e.g., favourite movies) at their own preferred time at home during the evening (two-hour-long movie from 19:00-23:00). The same use case is described in [MET15-D15]. The movie is typically transferred from a server to the user terminal when the movie is viewed. The challenge for this situation arises when most of the users in the same area want to experience their unique large sized media content at the same time. The users are located indoors. The service needs to be provided to all households that do not use the competitive alternative fixed connection. An outdoor to indoor propagation environment has to be considered, since Media on Demand is an indoor service provided with outdoor solutions.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	15Mbps	The data rate requirement depends on the quality of the video, which in turn depends on the resolution and the frame rate. A frame rate of 30 frames per second gives 12Mbps for 3840x2160 (4k), HEVC. A frame rate of 50 frames per second gives approx. 15Mbps.
User data rate in UL	Very low	The uplink must support the application signalling to get the video started, and a relatively high rate of TCP acknowledgements.
Connection density	4000/km ²	Assuming a city with a population density of 20000 people per km ² , on average two people per household, a service penetration of 100%, and a market share of 40%, the operator has 4000 household per km ² to serve. In the middle of the busy hour (at 21:00) all households will be watching movies.
Traffic Density	60Gbps/km ²	Per operator

Mobility	Static	
Availability	95%	With 15Mbps
Reliability	95%	
Latency	50ms	The absolute delay of starting the play out is not very strict. One or a few seconds, but less than 5s, is acceptable. However, to be able to quickly get up to speed (say 10Mbps) after possible link interruptions, a quite low delay is still desired, e.g. 50ms.

Gap from Current Technology

KPI	Requirement	Currently available
User data rate in DL	15Mbps	15 Mbps is achievable as a peak data rate per user with nowadays technology (i.e. 3GPP Rel-12 [NGMN15]). The problem comes when supporting several thousands of users at the same time and keeping the same data rate for all. Then the current technology needs to achieve higher spectrum efficiency by beamforming and MU-MIMO.
User data rate in UL	Very low	Uplink data required data rate is not stressing the system in this use case
Connection density	4000/km ²	According to [NGMN15] the typical in a dense urban area is up to up to 2000/km ² .
Traffic Density	60Gbps/km ²	A current LTE network with a spectral efficiency of 1bps/Hz/cell, 20MHz spectrum, and an ISD of 300m can supports 0.8Gbps/km ² . The requirement of 60Gbps/km ² is far beyond to what we can reach today.
Mobility	Static	
Availability	95%	The desire is of course to be able to reach every single household with the service. This is very impractical for radio-based services. Instead the target could be set to 99%, which is also very tough. An alternative is a target of 15Mbps for 95% of the households, and a target of 4Mbps for 99% of the households.
Reliability	95%	
Latency	50ms	TCP Round-Trip Time (RTT) of 100ms it takes approximately 5-7 RTTs (or 5-700ms) to grow the Congestion Window Size (CWND) to support 10Mbps. This also depends on the initial CWND. To avoid play-out interruptions, the buffers size

		should be larger than the TCP recovery time, which then is fulfilled with a buffer size of a couple of seconds. Note that the delay figure must hold also under loaded conditions. If TCP becomes a bottleneck, consider mitigating this, such as with a proxy, or an alternative transport protocol, e.g. UDP.
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4.1.2 Use Case 2: Cloud services

Description and Key Features

The main features of the 5G scenario “Cloud Services” are (cf. [NGMN15], [GSMA14], [MET13-D11])

- providing enhanced customization for individual users equipped with future mobile devices with higher display quality;
- fast responsiveness to support interactive applications (e.g. video conferencing, gaming [LLD15]), and possibly (real-time) processing of content/sensor data from the mobile devices for future monitoring, control, or big data analytics (e.g. self-driving cars);
- cloud services should be supported everywhere; however, this use case is focused on outdoor and larger indoor areas. An outdoor and (large) indoor propagation environment has to be studied.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	300Mbps	Future extremely high quality multimedia (8K, etc.) and cloud storage requiring extremely high capacities (0.5-1Gbps) are not in focus of this use case as a differentiator from other use cases (e.g. indoor)
User data rate in UL	50Mbps	Stemming mainly from video/data upload from end-user devices
Connection density	2500/km ²	Expected dense (non-crowd) urban connection density
Traffic Density	750 – 125 Gbps/km ²	For downlink and uplink, respectively
Mobility	100km/h	High speed performance up to 50km/h (typical city speed limit). Functional support up to 100km/h, as the highest expected velocity in dense urban scenarios
Availability	95%	Basic availability requirement for the 5G network
Reliability	95%	Basic reliability requirement for the 5G network
Latency	10ms	To support video-related applications (e.g., multi-person video conferencing)

We note that an inclusion of more advanced media technology, supported deployment (e.g. fast trains), or real-time remote computing requirements into the scope of cloud services use case would significantly change several KPI requirements (e.g. rate, mobility, latency). Therefore we excluded them from the use case scope.

Gap from Current Technology

This use case in its current form is partially beyond the 4G capabilities, as shown by the following table.

KPI	Requirement	Currently Available
User data rate in DL	300Mbps	Achievable as peak rate but not as UE experienced data rate in average (100Mbps) or at cell edge (significantly less) [DPS14], [NGMN15]
User data rate in UL	50Mbps	Achievable as peak but not as UE experienced data rate at cell edge (10-15Mbps for LTE-A) [DPS14], [NGMN15].
Connection density	2500/km ²	Typically up to 2000/km ² in dense urban areas [NGMN15]
Traffic Density	750 - 125Gbps/km ²	0.77Gbps/km ² (for spectral efficiency of 1bps/Hz/cell, 20MHz spectrum, ISD of 300m)
Mobility	100km/h	High speed performance up to 120 km/h, functional support up to 350km/h (but with lower rates), considerations of speeds up to 500km/h [SIM09]
Availability	95%	Not specified (treated as a business decision), but in practice it is taken as a coverage probability of a network (typically 95%) [GSMA14], [MET13-D11]
Reliability	95%	Not specified
Latency	10ms	In practice often 50ms E2E (10ms for 2 way RAN) [DPS14], [NGMN15]

4.1.3 Use Case 3: Dense urban society with distributed crowds

Description and Key Features

In urban dense areas, end users expect to have high capacity seamless connections to wireless services almost anywhere. Most of mobile networks users are either stationary or slowly moving. User's density and demands are variable: we consider a scenario in which in a dense urban area there are some locations with a massive crowd concentrated for some periods of time in small areas, (for public or sport events, concerts, etc). The kind of traffic is diversified: users can be interested in specific information during the event (scores, information about athletes or musicians, etc); they can watch HD video, share live video and or post on social networks. Crowds can be concentrated in an outdoor stadium, but also in an events hall (concerts, sport events indoor etc). To ensure uniform connectivity and uniform capacity, outdoor/indoor propagation is also of interest (stadiums have covered parts and access rings). Indoor, outdoor and outdoor/indoor propagation environments have then to be considered.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	25Mbps (up to 50Mbps)	For special events 25Mbps are considered sufficient. When urban dense society then the DL targets up to 50Mbps
User data rate in UL	50Mbps	Due to a massive sharing of HD video and photos the data rate is estimated higher in upload (~50Mbps)
Connection density	Peaks of 150000 users/km ² Average active users in stadium: 30000 users/stadium	In case of dedicated areas/structures (stadium or event areas), there may be heavy traffic peaks during the events, but the average load is lower. In a stadium (0.2km ²) the average number of active users is computed considering that in a stadium with capacity of 100000 people, 30% of users are in average active [NGMN15]
Traffic Density	Peaks DL: 3.75Tbps/km ² (DL stadium: 0.75Tbps/km ²) UL: 7.5Tbps/km ² (UL stadium: 1.5Tbps/km ²)	Connection density x user experience data rate
Mobility	Stationary/pedestrian	Users are either stationary or slowly moving
Availability	95%	Out of service minimization is a primary goal, related to massive presence of people in small places for short time frames
Reliability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions
Latency	10ms	The most critical issue is the sharing of real-time HD videos ensuring high quality user experience

The challenge is represented by the critical situation of massive crowds, while the urban dense area can be seen as a scenario with more relaxed constraints. To serve such amount of users, small cells able to connect to the self-configurable backhauling network have to be deployed.

Considering the real time sharing of multimedia contents, low latency –below 10 ms-- is also a required feature. Although at a first glance this KPI does not look critical (if compared to the lower latency required for other use cases), when coupled with the huge number of users, it becomes a stringent KPI.

Gap from Current Technology

KPI	Requirement	Currently available
User data rate in DL	25Mbps	This data rate in DL is already available in LTE, but it becomes critical when

		considering the number of users to be served simultaneously
User data rate in UL	50 Mbps	In LTE the user data rate is currently limited to 50Mbps UL as peak, not as average
Connection density	Average active users in stadium: 30000 users/stadium Peaks of 150000 users/km ²	An ultra-high connection density as the one required from this use case cannot be reached yet (currently the capability is around 2000users/km ² [NGMN15]).
Traffic Density	Peaks UL: 7.5Tbps/km ² DL: 3.75Tbps/km ²	The required traffic density cannot be supported by the current technology
Mobility	Stationary/pedestrian	Currently achievable
Availability	95%	Not possible with the current technology to avoid outage of service, when massive crowds are present
Reliability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions
Latency	10ms	Currently 10ms for 2-way RAN but typically up to 50ms if other factors are considered

4.1.5 Use Case 4: Smart offices

Description and Key Features

Indoor ultra-high broadband access allows communication with an increasing number of devices, with very different constraints (bandwidth intensive for all devices transmitting video, or with critical latency requirements for home automation devices for example). Typically this use-case covers indoor communications in homes and apartments as well as office buildings involving a high density of devices. The traffic pattern in smart office use-cases can however be very different. Smart-office applications may either generate localized traffic, which can be routed in the first access node or a few local hops while use-cases like video sharing generate traffic, which needs to be routed through the core network. Localized traffic could even be supported by Device-2-Device communication. With respect to the propagation environment, indoor and outdoor to indoor (limited at cm and mm-wave frequencies) have to be considered.

Key Performance Indicators

The values below are based on the [NGMN15] scenario “smart office”. The alternative values in the comment are based on [MET13-D11] scenario “virtual reality office”. The requirements from [MET13-D11] are more stringent.

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	1Gbps Average load 0.2Gbps/user	Cloud storage service [MET13-D11] states 1Gbps/5Gbps with average load 0.5Gbps/user
User data rate in UL	500Mbps Average load 0.027Gbps/user	Cloud storage service [MET13-D11] states 1Gbps/5Gbps with average load 0.5Gbps/user
Connection density	75000/km ²	[MET13-D11] states 0.5Gbps per user and 100Mbps/m ² which yields 200000/km ²
Traffic Density	15Tbps/km ² (DL) 2Tbps/km ² (UL)	Based on a mix of services “cloud storage”, “Desk cloud service”, “Multiparty video” and other services with negligible rate contribution, see [NGMN15]. The average DL/UL rates for an active user is 200Mbps/25Mbps, 5Mbps/1Mbps, 3Mbps/0.75Mbps for the three categories in total 208Mbps/26.75Mbps. [MET13-D11] states 100 Tbps/km ²
Mobility	Pedestrian	[MET13-D11] states “Static or low mobility nomadic (less than 6km/hr)”
Availability	500Mbps and 1Gbps in UL and DL with 95% availability.	[MET13-D11] 1Gbps, UL and DL, with 95% availability (5Gbps with 20% availability)
Reliability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions [MET13-D11] states 99% working hours
Latency	10ms E2E latency	General requirement for 5G, see [NGMN15]. [MET13-D11] states 10msRTT MAC-layer

Gap from Current Technology

KPI	Requirement	Currently available
User data rate in DL	1Gbps Average load 0.2 Gbps/user	LTE peak downlink rate is 4Gbps in the release 12 [NGMN15]. 802.11ad standard includes rates up to 6.756Gbps. Qualcomm announced 4.6Gbps chip February 2014, [POE:14]. 802.11ac standard includes rates up to 4.9Gbps. The RT-AC3200 router from ASUS is claimed to deliver 1.3Gbps in the 5GHz band per client [NGO:15]. 5GHz antennas are bulky compared to mm-wave.

		Actual rates in loaded network significantly lower than above stated.
User data rate in UL	500Mbps Average load 0.027Gbps/user	LTE peak uplink rate 1.5Gbps. 802.11ad standard includes rates up to 6.756Gbps. Qualcomm announced 4.6Gbps chip February 2014, [POE:14]. 802.11ac standard includes rates up to 4.9Gbps. The RT-AC3200 router from ASUS is claimed to deliver 1.3Gbps in the 5GHz band per client [NGO:15]. 5GHz antennas are bulky compared to mm-wave. Actual rates in loaded network significantly lower than above stated.
Connection density	75000/km ²	2000/km ² [NGMN15]
Traffic Density	15Tbps/km ² (DL) 2Tbps/km ² (UL)	Wi-Fi suffers from the following problems with extensive spatial re-use: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inefficient under high load due to the limitation of contention based access, - Interference from APs in the same network (e.g. same SSID) and uncoordinated interference from independently deployed networks Interference from other technologies (e.g. Bluetooth, microwave ovens, radar and satellite)
Mobility	Static or pedestrian	802.11ad aims at cable replacement. LTE and 802.11ac handles this mobility with ease.
Availability	500Mbps and 1Gbps in UL and DL with 95% availability.	
Reliability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions
Latency	10ms	25ms end-to-end latency in 4G with content at the edge, [NGMN15].

4.1.5 Use Case 5: Immersive early 5G experience in targeted coverage

Description and Key Features

As with early deployments of previous mobile generations (3G/4G), 5G mobile deployments will be initially required to provide targeted/limited coverage for the early adopters. This is most likely to be in dense urban traffic hot-spots, with mm-wave small cells. Some of the

early adopters would particularly want to experience immersive multi-media provided by 5G services, including 4k/8k UHD video, virtual reality and real time mobile gaming. These 5G experiences should come with a palpable improvement from the QoE of users compared to the (then) legacy 4G services. For the immersive multi-media experiences, the ‘user experienced’ data rates, latencies and other key KPIs should indicate a step change from the (then) 4G evolutions.

In determining the key KPIs for this use case, we have to consider the likely requirements of the evolving immersive applications and the likely capabilities the evolving 4G systems would provide. Currently the 4k UHD video streaming services promoted in UK needs at least 40Mbps consistent data-rates [TRD15], which is today only possible with wired/satellite connections. With 8k UHD and further evolutions these requirements are likely to increase many fold. Today’s -Advanced specifications can provide around 10Mbps user experienced data rates and 1Gbps peak data rates for static users. The latencies supported by IMTAdvanced specs are around 50ms. The proposed key KPIs for this 5G use case are: 100Mbps as a baseline data rate, while the peak data rates (on demand) can be up to 20Gbps and the latencies to be below 10ms. The large variance in data rates is to support the potential requirements of the evolving immersive 5G applications and also to account for the possible variations in radio link quality. The 20Gbps peak rate can seem excessive at first glance. However, other technologies like WiGig are already proposing peak rates of around 7Gbps and IEEE 802.11 Next Generation 60GHz study group are considering data rates above 20Gbps for short range applications [IEEENG60-14]. New services will emerge in this context and 5G needs to stay competitive with such data rates.

These initial 5G hotspots, deployed on mm-wave spectrum, will have an underlay coverage provided by 3G, 4G or even sub 6GHz 5G systems. Thus the 5G hotspot small cells will be supported by an underlay of macro cells from these technologies. The interworking, handover coordination between these 5G hotspots and the underlay network will be an important feature for this use case.

With respect to the propagation environment, deployments such as outdoor to indoor and indoor to indoor have to be considered.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	>100 Mbps	The user could demand higher data rates up to 20Gbps. The network should be flexible to support these rates.
User data rate in UL	>50 Mbps	The user could demand higher data rates up to 10Gbps.
Connection density	~10000/km ²	Estimated 1000 active users in a 0.1km ² hotspot area is supported by 40 users in each of 25 small cells.
Traffic Density	1.7/0.85 Tbps per hotspot area (0.1km ²) 17/8.5Tbps per km ²	For downlink and uplink, respectively. It is assumed that 50% active users demand around 100Mbps in DL, while 4% users demand around 10-20Gbps.
Mobility	0-5 km/h	The mobility is low, with most users moving at pedestrian speed.
Availability	Above 95%	Enabler for 5G services, as a step change from 4G.

Reliability	Above 95%	Enabler for 5G services, as a step change from 4G.
Latency	Below 10ms	To support 5G real time gaming and VR applications.

Gap from Current Technology

As noted above, the user experienced data rate should improve by a factor of 10 and the peak data rates should improve by a factor of 20 from the current LTE levels. The latencies should be reduced by at least by a factor of 5 to achieve (near) real time experience in immersive 5G services. One of the deployment challenges (w.r.t. LTE) would be the densification of the small cells. We believe that around 25 small cells per hotspot area (typically 0.1km²) would be required to provide the necessary capacity and the number of connections. Interference control and back-haul provision technologies will have to significantly improve from the current state-of-the-art.

In this comparison, the small cell specific LTE state of the art technology has to be referenced. LTE-Hi (LTE for Hotspot and indoor) is an emerging technology, with the specifications expected to be finalised in LTE release 13. A recent IEEE paper by experts of two tier 1 operators [NNB+13] estimated that this technology will achieve 838Mbps peak data rates with 100MHz compound (carrier aggregated) bandwidth. The cell sizes they foresee are up to 50m radius. The link spectral efficiency is already high (8.38bits/Hz). We can expect the combined value of higher density and spectral efficiency (area spectral efficiency) to go up by a factor of 4 under favourable conditions in early 5G. This is also considering that the multi-antenna phased arrays having to mostly support SNR gain in beam-forming, but also achieving higher spatial re-use/multiplexing gains. With the pedestrian mobility and interference effects considered, making these cells very small can be counter-productive. So to achieve the 20Gbps peak data rate, the bandwidth factor needs to go up at least by a factor of 6. Thus the initial bandwidth requirement for this use case (for a provision of peak rate to a single user) alone would be 600MHz. We consider the peak spectral density values (per specific link) rather than the area spectral densities considered in some other use cases, as the peak data rate provision is a major requirement in this use case. The above requirements and the gap from current technology are summarised in the Table below:

KPI	Requirement	Currently available
User data rate in DL	>100Mbps	The current 'user experienced' data rates are around 10Mbps for LTE (in dense urban favourable conditions).
User data rate in DL (peak)	Up to 20Gbps	LTE small cell enhancements (LTE-Hi) are claiming to achieve up to 838Mbps in hotspots [NNB+13]. The proposed 5G rates are markedly higher.
Connection density	10000/km ²	Currently LTE systems can handle around 2000users/km ² – but at much lower cell-edge rates [NGMN15].
Traffic Density	1.7/0.85Tbps per 0.1km ² area 17/8.5Tbps per km ²	The required traffic density cannot be supported by the current technology.
Mobility	0-5km/h	Currently available but not for such a high user data rate

Availability	Above 95%	95% availability requirement for LTE
Reliability	Above 95%	95% reliability requirement for LTE
Latency	Below 10ms	Currently achievable as best-case but typically up to 50ms if other factors are considered.

4.2 Broadband access everywhere

Broadband access everywhere refers here in creating an edgeless RAN. However in [NGMN15] it refers to the provision of broadband (not necessarily high speeds but rather with ultra-low cost requirements) in remote/rural/less well-off areas.

4.2.1 Use Case 6: 50+Mbps everywhere

Description and Key Features

NGMN, when defining this use case [NGMN15], indicates that the mobile and connected society will need broadband access to be available everywhere. Therefore, 50Mbps should be understood as the minimum user data rate and not a single user's theoretical peak rate. Furthermore, it is emphasized that this user rate has to be delivered consistently across the coverage area, even at cell edge [IWPC14]. The target value of 50Mbps, or possibly 100Mbps (or even 1Gbps) everywhere is meant to be indicative, depending upon the 5G technology evolution to support these figures in an economically viable manner. With respect to the propagation environment, all types of deployments have to be considered.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	>50Mbps	Target value could be 100Mbps, or even 1Gbps
User data rate in UL	25Mbps	
Connection density	400-2500/km ²	Expected dense (non-crowded) urban connection density. Starting with a user density of 140users/km ² to be supported in LTE, the x4 increase expected for 5G means that user density increases to 560user/km ² . Assuming 4 operators, this translates to 2240 users/km ² in dense urban environment. In sub-urban settings this may go down to 400/km ²
Traffic Density	28 - 14Gbps/km ²	For DL and UL, respectively, for 560 users with 50 and 25Mbps data rates, respectively. It will go down to 20/10 Gbps/km ² in sub-urban.
Mobility	50km/h	High speed performance up to 50km/h (typical city speed limit). Functional support up to 120km/h, as the highest expected velocity in dense urban scenarios
Availability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions
Reliability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions

Latency	10ms	To support video-related applications
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Gap from Current Technology

The NGMN [NGMN15] foresees three main drivers to achieve this objective: increase of the spectral efficiency by a factor of 5, of the cell density (with the deployment of small cells) by a factor of 8 and of the spectrum resources; for this last point, the working assumption is that mm-wave spectrum is only considered if the objective cannot be achieved using spectral resources below 6GHz.

On the other hand, the density of active users in 5G is expected to increase by a factor of 4.

The cell edge DL spectral efficiency in LTE Release 10 with MIMO 2x2 being 0.07bps/Hz/user (and only half that on the UL), the 5G cell edge spectral efficiency should be then 0.35 bps/Hz/user.

The increase of cell density, compensated by the increase of users, results in a net increase of 2 of the resources available per user with respect to LTE.

Assuming that all the spectrum resources are available for the user, and assuming 50 MHz per operator available below 6GHz, the cell edge bit rate that can be supported would be:

$$0.35\text{bps/Hz/user} \times 2 \times 50\text{MHz} = 35\text{Mbps/user.}$$

To achieve the required bit rate a downlink bandwidth larger than 71 MHz would be required. However, it cannot be assumed that all the frequency resources will be available for a single user during the busy hour for the time window associated. In consequence, it seems clear that more spectrum than the 71MHz estimated is required, either for supporting directly cell edge users or for liberating resources in low frequency ranges to support them.

On the other hand, in rural and suburban environments it cannot be expected that the densification will happen. Then the requirement for cell edge provision of 50 Mbps should rely on the increase of the spectral efficiency and the availability of additional spectrum. In this sense, it is important to highlight that rural sites are usually fitted with only low frequency carriers that maximize coverage.

The above requirements and the gap from current technology are summarised in the Table below:

KPI	Requirement	Currently available
User data rate in DL	>50Mbps	LTE-A provides "at least" 2.40bps/Hz/cell (using 2x2 MIMO) but this is much lower per user: 0.07bps/Hz/user. This equates to 1.4Mbps DL cell-edge rate for an operating BW of 20MHz
User data rate in UL	25Mbps	On the UL the cell-edge spectral efficiency in LTE-A is 0.04bps/Hz, resulting in sub-1Mbps rates on the UL for 20MHz of BW
Connection density	400-2500/km ²	Currently the systems can handle around 2000users/km ² – but at much lower cell-edge rates as explained above
Traffic Density	28/14Gbps/km ²	The required traffic density cannot be supported by the current technology
Mobility	50km/h	Currently available but not for such a high user data rate

Availability	95%	Basic availability requirement for the 5G network
Reliability	95%	Basic availability requirement for the 5G network
Latency	10ms	Currently achievable as best-case but typically up to 50ms if other factors are considered

4.3 High Mobility Users

In the future there will be a growing demand for the broadband mobile communication in vehicles (trains, buses, cars) and even aircrafts. We can distinguish the following use cases which depend on required degree of mobility:

- High Speed Trains
- Moving vehicles (cars, buses, etc.)
- Moving crowds (e.g., moving mass events such as walking/cycling demos or a long red-cycle of a traffic light)
- Aircraft Connectivity

The growing number of communication services for higher mobility users require diverse requirements depending on use case characteristic. Vehicles will demand in-vehicle entertainment, access to the internet, advanced navigation, autonomous driving, safety and vehicle diagnostics.

4.3.1 Use Case 7: Moving Hot Spots

Description and key features

In this use case we focus on high speed trains and moving vehicles (cars, buses) with the perspective of accessing to mobile broadband networks for in-vehicle entertainment and Internet services. The advanced navigation, autonomous driving and safety features are out of the scope because they are characterized by completely different sets of requirements.

The speed of the vehicles could be from low speed in cities (cars and buses) to greater than 500km/h (in high speed train). The vehicles speed range from low to very high causes that providing mobile services with high QoE will become a challenge.

As for propagation environment to be considered, we can distinguish two cases:

- vehicles with an installed antenna or relay node: outdoor propagation between the BS and the antenna on the vehicle plus the indoor propagation inside the vehicle between such relay and user equipment.
- vehicles without antenna or relay node: outdoor and in/out propagation between the BS and user equipment.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	50Mbps	50Mbps of DL throughput is required for typical Internet applications like HD video,

		video conference, gaming, music listening, social networking, information reading, accessing company intranet etc. [NGMN15]
User data rate in UL	2Mbps	25Mbps of UL throughput is required for typical Internet applications like video conference, gaming, social networking, accessing company intranet etc. [NGMN15]
Connection density	2000users/km ²	500 active users per train x 4 trains or 20 active users per bus x 100 buses or 1 active user per car x 2000 cars Traffic assumptions: - Trains assumptions: 1000 persons per train, 50% activity factor, 2 trains per route (in opposite directions) within 1km ² , 2 routes within 1km ² - Cars assumptions (traffic jam case): 1000 cars are distributed over a 4-way x 4-way highway segment of 1km length; 2 highways within 1km ² , 2 persons per car, 50% activity factor. - Buses assumptions (traffic jam case): 50 buses are distributed over a 4-way x 4-way highway segment of 1km length; 2 highways within 1km ² , 40 persons per bus, 50% activity factor. [NGMN15]
Traffic Density	DL: 100Gbps/km ² UL: 50 Gbps/km ²	Connection density x User experienced data rate DL: 25Gbps per train, 1Gbps per bus, 50Mbps per car UL: 12.5Gbps per train, 0.5Gbps per bus, 25Mbps per car [NGMN15]
Mobility	30-500km/h	From low speed of cars and buses to high speed trains.
Availability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions
Reliability	95%	Basic requirements for 5G solutions
Latency	10ms	10ms of latency could be required for real time HD video

From the KPI's point of view, the challenge is to achieve the required capacity for large range of vehicles speed and different environments where vehicles are moving. The dynamic backhaul setup and fast cells handovers are especially important in the high speed cases like trains.

We can distinguish the following characteristics for two mentioned cases:

- Vehicles with an installed antenna or relay node:

Equipment are connected to the relay hence guarantying stationary radio channel but requiring dynamic backhaul during the movement of the vehicle. The installation of antenna/relay on the vehicle is mandatory for access system on mm-wave frequency bands.

The other option for this case is the installation of a complete Access Point (AP) on the vehicle (e.g. train) which is connected to the network via wireless backhaul (e.g. mm-

waves dynamic backhaul). The AP with antenna installed inside the vehicle will guarantee the required coverage.

- Vehicles without antenna or relay node

Equipment are connected to network BS hence implying very dynamic radio channel during the movement of the vehicles. This setup requires fast handovers during the vehicle's movement. The performance of the mobile services in this case will be much lower than in the case of antenna/relay installed on the vehicle.

This case is only possible for lower frequencies due to penetration loss constraints.

Gap from Current Technology

KPI	Requirement	Currently available
User data rate in DL	50Mbps	Currently achievable but could be a challenge for high speed vehicle and large number of users to be served
User data rate in UL	25Mbps	Currently achievable but could be a challenge for high speed vehicle and large number of users to be served
Connection density	2000users/km ²	The 2000users/km ² [NGMN15] of connection density are currently achievable for stationary and pedestrian users but for high speed of vehicle this requirement is not achievable
Traffic Density	DL: 100Gbps/km ² UL: 50Gbps/km ²	This requirement is achievable for low speed and not achievable for high speed of vehicle
Mobility	30-500km/h	In 3GPP Rel.12: functional up to 350km/h (for certain bands up to 500km/h) [NGMN15]. 5G should support mobility up to 500km/h for all frequency ranges
Availability	95%	This requirement is achievable for low speed and not achievable for high speed of vehicle
Reliability	95%	This requirement is achievable for low speed and not achievable for high speed of vehicle. The reliable fast handovers are required
Latency	10ms	This requirement is achievable for low speed and not achievable for high speed of vehicle

The current technologies do not have the potential for establishing dynamic backhauling for high speed vehicle and achieving fast handovers in case of high mobility.

4.4 Extreme real time or ultra-reliable communication

With the advent of improved tele-control techniques and assisted control of objects, several industries have benefited from the possibility to perform surgeries in remote and secure places

instead of in-situ. Reliable connectivity in ultra-low latency conditions for extreme real time communication can be foreseen in applications such as remote driving or flying of unmanned vehicles, robotic control, remote health, remote augmented reality, etc.

In all cases, end-to-end latency should not exceed very few ms irrespective of the channel conditions. This gives rise to several interesting yet highly challenging use cases, among which “Tactile internet” is perhaps the best representative.

In parallel, the family of ultra-reliable communications comprises use cases like automated traffic control and driving, robot networking, remote surgery and further applications related to 3D connectivity and public safety [NGMN15]. In the context of utilizing higher frequencies for mobile networks, the remote surgery use case is of particular interest, since it entails high requirements in terms of latency in combination with video stream transmission.

Regarding the propagation environment, indoor and outdoor media has to be considered. In fact maximum distance between transmitter and receiver should not be greater than 100 m so as not to compromise latency; therefore deployments would likely be indoors (but not precluding some controlled outdoors situations).

4.4.1 Use Case 8: Tactile Internet, remote surgery

Description and key features

Tactile interaction is only perceived as natural when the delay between the tactile senses and the associated result is in the millisecond range. Therefore a high responsiveness is to be expected from the radio interface as well as the network nodes involved. The maximum distance between end points should therefore be small to moderate (up to 100m), and the amount of information to be transmitted is also expected to be small (in the range of 1Mbps or less).

Remote surgery, or tele-surgery, allows a surgeon to perform a surgery on a patient, though they are not at the same location [MLR+02]. Sitting at a surgeon console (master controller), the surgeon can remotely control surgical instruments of a robot by moving his hand, fingers and wrists [DV12], [HB10]. A visual feedback is the most dominant form of interaction, since 3D High Definition (HD) provides the highest density of information [DV12]. Current systems make use of fixed networks in hospitals. With mobile technology, it would be possible to carry out even complex, time-critical surgeries in ambulances and at remote disaster sites, where no surgeons are available.

As propagation environment, tactile Internet and remote surgery should target both outdoor to indoor and indoor to indoor coverage.

Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Requirement	Comment
User data rate in DL	1Mbps for tactile applications; 50Mbps for remote-robot surgery or video augmented robotic control	User throughput would be up to 1 Mbps except for remote surgery and video augmented robotic control where downlink throughput could be up to 50Mbps
User data rate in UL	1Mbps	Real-time control information
Connection density	330users/km ² for tactile applications ; 10users/km ² for remote surgery	For the critical applications, the system should be defined in order to be able to cope with these connection densities without service interruption. Nevertheless, it is unlikely to have more than 10 active connections per deployment areas e.g.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tactile internet: approx. 100m radius (0.03km²). - remote surgery: multiple ambulances at remote disaster site within 1km²
Traffic density	<p><i>For video augmented robotic control:</i> DL: 16Gbps/km² UL: 330Mbps/km²</p> <p><i>For tactile applications</i> DL and UL: 330Mbps/km²</p> <p><i>For remote surgery</i> DL: 500Mbps/km² UL: 10Mbps/km²</p>	<p>Calculation considers 10 simultaneous users, 50Mbps per user in DL for remote-robot surgery or video augmented robotic control / 1Mbps per user in UL, 0.03km² deployment area and the connection density above</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for tactile applications and video-augmented robotic control: cell radius 100m, hence 330users/km² - for remote-robot surgery: 10users/km² <p>Thus traffic density results from calculating (bit_rate) x (user_density), hence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for video augmented robotic control: 16Gbps/km² (DL), 330Mbps/km² (UL) - for tactile applications: 330Mbps/km² - for remote surgery: 500Mbps/km² (DL), 10Mbps/km² (UL)
Mobility	Little or no mobility	<p>Ultra-low latency operation precludes any significant mobility;</p> <p>Remote-robot manipulation surgery requires no mobility</p>
Availability	99.999% within the event area for critical applications* 95% for non-critical applications*	Very high availability for critical services
Reliability	99.999% for critical applications* 95% for non-critical applications*	Very high reliability for critical services
Latency	<p><i>For tactile internet:</i> 1ms</p> <p><i>For remote surgery:</i> 10ms</p>	For tactile internet, one-way latency should not be higher than 1ms. For remote surgery, where the propagation time has also to be taken into account, 10ms is sufficient

* critical application=remote health, robotic control; non critical=remote gaming, remote augmented reality

System key features related to data transmission are ultra-reliable, secure connections with a video packet error rate well below 1% and very low latency in both directions.

The ability of the surgery to carry out the procedure fast and accurately is heavily dependent on the degree of life-like feeling the system can provide. High and varying latency and jitter results in extreme degradation of performance [FLC+00], [HB10].

For the telesurgery application, which is highly dependent on the video quality, it is important to aim for near error-free transmission with a maximum packet loss rate below 0.01%. Under any circumstances it must be excluded that unauthorized persons can disturb the link or even take control [Sto15].

Gap from Current Technology

There is no way to actually fulfil these requirements and KPIs with current state of the art. Fundamental changes to radio access techniques and associated numerology are required, as well as significant simplification of the network architecture to reduce latency to the minimum. State of the art 4G technology usually provide latency values around 25ms. Therefore the gap can be at least 24ms, and would be progressively higher as long as 5G latency shrinks below 1ms.

KPI	Requirement	Currently Available
User data rate in DL	50Mbps / 1Mbps	Achievable with current technology
User data rate in UL	1Mbps	Achievable with current technology
Connection density	330users/km ²	Currently achievable
Traffic density	DL for video augmented robotic control: 16Gbps/km ² DL for tactile applications, and UL: 320Mbps/km ² DL for remote surgery 500Mbps/km ²	Currently achievable
Mobility	Little or no mobility	Currently achievable
Availability	99.999% for critical applications; 95% for non-critical applications	Currently achievable only in ultra-dense environments
Reliability	99.999% within the event area for critical applications; 95% for non-critical applications	Not currently achievable
Latency	1ms one-way	Not currently achievable (not less than 25ms one-way latency is achievable with current technology)

Packet loss requirement of 0.01% for remote-surgery applications is not achievable with current technology and some improvement of 1-2 orders of magnitude would be required.

4.5 KPIs summary and technology definition

In the previous sections some use cases interesting for the mmMAGIC project have been described. The selected use cases are not meant to be a comprehensive list, but rather a

selection of representative use cases useful to define a technology for extreme Mobile broadband applications. For each use case a list of KPIs has been defined. In Table 4-1, in order to have a global view, we summarize the KPIs and requirements.

	Broadband access in dense Areas					Broadband access everywhere	High user mobility	E-real time communication and Ultrareliable
	Use Case 1	Use Case 2	Use case 3	Use case 4	Use Case 5	Use case 6	Use case 7	Use Case 8
	Media on demand	Cloud services	Dense urban Society with distributed crowds	Smart Office	Immersive early 5G experience in targeted hot-spots	50+Mbps everywhere	Moving Hot Spots	Tactile internet / Video augmented robotic control and Remote-robot manipulation surgery
User Data Rate in DL [Mbps]	15	300	25 (up to 50)	1000 (average load 0,2 Gbps/user)	100	50	50	50
User Data Rate in UL [Mbps]	Very low	50	50	500 (average load 0,027 Gbps/user)	50	25	25	1
Connection density [user/km ²]	4000	2500	30000 (with peaks of 150000)	75000	10000	400-2500	2000	330
Traffic Density DL/UL [Gbps/Km ²]	60	750 / 150	peaks : 3750/7500	15000/2000	1700 / 850 per hotspot area (0,1km ²)	28/14	100/50	16 / 0,32
mobility [km/h]	Stationary / Pedestrian	100	Stationary / Pedestrian	Pedestrian	Stationary / Pedestrian	Pedestrian to 50Km/h	30-500Km/h	Stationary / Pedestrian
Availability[%]	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	99.999
Reliability[%]	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	99.999
Latency [ms]	50	10	10	10	10	10	10	1
Deployment	O-I	All	All	O-I and I-I	O-I and I-I	All	All	I-I and O-I

Table 4-1 KPIs summary for the Use considered use cases

From the Table 4-1 it can be seen that some use cases have the same requirements and that some KPIs have critical values for a specific use case. By analysing this table in a critical way, it is possible then to derive some directions to be followed in order to design a common technology that, with some peculiar modifications, can be adapted to the different use cases.

These use cases will be investigated by system-level and link-level simulations, which can be defined as:

- **Link-level simulations:** Link-level simulations in mmMAGIC will focus on performance of links, which can be single link (point-to-point) or multi-link (point-to-multi-point, multi-point-to-point, multi-point-to-multi-point). Usually, the details of PHY and /or MAC layers are captured in the simulations, where transmissions and evaluations are down to bit/symbol level. From link-level simulation results, abstraction of PHY and certain MAC properties can be derived for system model simulation. A typical interface between link- and system- level simulation is the SINR to BER mapping curve/table. Link level simulations allow for the investigation of issues such as Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) gains, Adaptive Modulation and Coding (AMC) feedback, modelling of channel encoding and decoding or physical layer modelling for system-level [IWR10].
- **System-level simulations:** The system-level simulations will focus more on network-related issues such as resource allocation (scheduling), fast handover for mobility

handling, interference management (including inter-beam interference management), multi-connectivity which involves multi-cell BSs clustering, C/U plane splitting, etc. System-level evaluations would comprise multiple users and cells where interactions between users and/or cells are to be analysed either dynamically (i.e. in the time domain) or statistically (i.e. with Monte Carlo method). The actual coverage of protocol layers in the simulations would depend on the desired approach, spanning from multi-cell L1 processing to modelling elements from the higher layers (for mobility, multi connectivity, RRM, etc.).

Use cases 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 8 will be investigated through system level simulations, while use cases 5 and 7 will be analysed through link level evaluations. Figure 4-1 summarizes the use cases to be investigated in mmMAGIC.

Figure 4-1 mmMAGIC use cases

5 Advantages and challenges of using mm-waves

Wider bandwidth is the key factor to fulfil the mobile broadband services where users density is high (some examples of use cases are video on demand, dense urban and smart office), demanding higher data rates than currently available, resulting in traffic density in the orders of several Gbps/km². The mm-wave frequency range offers the possibility to find wider contiguous bandwidth. For some use cases (e.g. tactile Internet, cloud services, remote surgery) the need for large continuous bandwidth can be justified by the simplicity of processing at rendering devices used to access the cloud (simplified MAC techniques), combined with latency and energy requirements, might not allow sophisticated encoding methods and will require transmission of raw multimedia data, thus requiring large bandwidths. Moreover, the high directionality of the antennas causes less interference to other mm-wave systems.

In dense urban areas, where it is expected that many 5G small cells will be deployed so to boost capacity, unfavourable propagation characteristics from mm-waves will not be a main hindrance, thus allowing high frequency reuse due to the increased path loss compared the lower frequencies and improving isolation due to narrow-beams - even with antennas with small form factor. All this is an advantage for backhauling and access when static crowds are targeted (e.g., in a stadium). However when a ubiquitous data rate (50+Mbps) needs to be provided everywhere, a new definition of the building blocks in the 5G architecture is needed, in order to guarantee that users with the least favourable conditions get enough resources to obtain 50 Mbps during the period of time required by the application, so that the user's experience is not degraded. In this context, it is a likely conclusion that the resources in low frequency ranges are enough for supporting the expected throughput of 50Mbps for users at the cell edge. This most likely means that in order to attach other users (who may be in more favourable conditions) additional resources are needed that can only be found in higher frequency ranges. For broadcast application, higher frequencies enable transmission of information to dedicated areas, thus avoiding the effect of blurring other areas.

The main disadvantage of using mm-wave is that availability, reliability, and throughput consistency in the seamless networking context cannot be ensured (particularly if the mm-wave system is a standalone one), due to blocking created by obstacles and people. In those cases of lack of coverage, relaying may be a solution. Locating core network functions closer to the user will be required to improve the end-to-end fast responsiveness of the overall system. Another challenge is to support medium speed mobility on high frequencies in urban conditions. For the access link, mm-waves can represent a significant challenge when moving massive crowds (e.g., sport events like marathons) are gathered in small areas with high probability of shadowing the link. The challenges are in establishing the reliable backhauling for high speed vehicle (fast beam tracing, obstacles) and achieving fast handovers in the access link. Planning of how to position access points, tracking the connection to them and initiating fast handovers could be key to a reliable, high-data rate mm-wave access link. Last but not least, outdoor to indoor coverage is another when going to higher frequencies.

6 Frequency Map and KPI Assessment

Governments and policy makers have recognised the economic and societal importance that can be attached to the robust delivery of digital services. Forecasts predict that the huge increase in consumer demand for data services driven by access to ever smarter and powerful devices is expected to continue beyond 2020. Accordingly many academic, industrial and policy initiatives have started to consider the development of next generation 5G mobile networks and the capabilities they will require to meet the future demands. Central to this topic is the discussion about the future radio spectrum requirements and the identification of new spectrum resources that are appropriate to the 5G research and technological activities.

The mmMAGIC project is focusing research on the use of frequency bands from 6GHz to 100GHz. These frequencies are of interest due to the possibilities to identify wider contiguous bandwidths that can efficiently deliver very high data rates. The purpose of this section is to provide some initial analysis of the frequency bands in the ranges of 6-100GHz, on the usage for mobile cellular services. The 51-70GHz band, where the bands for unlicensed wireless usage reside, has been excluded from this analysis as it is not part of the research undertaken by the mmMAGIC project, as per the project proposal. This analysis is mainly based on collating information on the frequency allocations for mobile services and the field trials/studies carried out in these frequency ranges. The main purpose is to provide a reference guide for the reader to check the existence of cm and mm-wave allocations for mobile usage and any recent activity from the industry/academia in these bands.

In this deliverable, the analysis looks not just at the ‘existence’ of frequency ranges for mobile operations but also at assessing suitability of frequency ranges on key KPIs. The term ‘existence’ is used to describe frequency ranges which have at least been assigned on a co-primary basis for mobile operations by the ITU. A service allocated spectrum on a primary basis can expect to be protected from interference from secondary services and is not required to protect secondary services. Co-primary services would need to ensure protection of each other’s services if they both bring the band into use. . Notice that the allocation for a band to mobile service is not necessarily the same as the usage of the band by mobile broadband systems. A colour coded frequency map, under a clearly defined set of KPIs, is developed and provided in this public version of the deliverable.

At this early stage of the project and of 5G in general, it is more prudent to look at the existence/suitability of wider frequency ranges rather than at specific bands. With this approach in mind, the total spectrum is divided into 3 frequency ranges and the analysis is provided for each frequency range. These are the 6-31GHz as Low GHz range, 31-51GHz as Mid GHz range and 71-100GHz range as High GHz range. It is worth noting that the split points for these ranges do not carry much significance and the ranges have been identified mostly to ease the analysis.

The identification of harmonised spectrum requires international collaboration and already the ITU World Radio Conference to be held in November 2015 (WRC-2015) is expected to discuss these matters to initiate studies that can result in the identification of suitable spectrum in 2019. The WRC-2015 activities will be driven by a number of regional and multi-country proposals from around the globe that are proposing firstly the topic is placed on the agenda for the future 2019 conference and secondly have proposed a range of higher frequency bands to be considered for study. The common regional proposals for bands to be studied are summarised Table 6-1:

GHz	6-31	31-50	Above 50
Asia Pacific (APT)	25.25-25.5	31.8-33.4 39-47 47.2-50.2	50.4-52.6 66-76 81-86
Europe (CEPT)	24.5-27.5	31.8-33.4 40.5-43.5	66-71 71-76

		45.5-48.9	81-86
Americas (CITEL)	10-10.45	31.8-33	50.4-52.6
	23.15-23.6	37-40.5	59.3-76
	24.25-27.5	45.5-47	
	27.5-29.5	47.2-50.2	

Table 6-1 Regional proposed frequency bands

6.1 Spectrum Survey and Analysis

The aim of this section is to provide a survey of previous studies on the feasibility of utilizing the aforementioned frequency ranges for mobile operations. These studies vary from channel measurements to full prototype system implementations.

Low GHz range:

At the regulatory level (ITU-R Working Party 5D and Ofcom) there are currently discussions on the technical feasibility for the bands above 6GHz [OFCOM15], and [ITU15]. In the current available literature it can be found that [RER+95] and [AE00] have created channel measurements and models for the 6GHz and 10GHz, respectively. Full prototypes for mobile systems implemented in this range have not yet been found.

In the 11-21GHz frequency range, 15GHz is the one for which industries showed demonstrations and trial since it has been available by regulators. A 5G-like prototype has been provided at this frequency by Ericsson and NTT DoCoMo [ERIC15a],[ERIC15b], and [ERIC15c]. Such a testbed is the first step of a three-phases trial that should lead to a fully integrated system by end of 2017.

The primary studies in the upper-part of Low GHz frequency range have been conducted around 28GHz, where some key measurements, modelling and system demos have been carried out. Samsung Electronics has conducted a series of field measurements in Korea and in Texas, US. In the latest trials in October 2014, data rates of 7.5Gbps for stationary users and 1.2Gbps for mobile users moving at 100km/h speeds have been achieved [S14]. The use of advanced beamforming technology is the key to overcome path losses and achieve these data rates. Details about the beam-forming algorithm and the prototype developed can be found in [RSP14]. Several channel models have been published based on these measurement analyses [HUR15-1, HUR15-2].

The New York University (NYU) has also conducted notable channel measurements at 28GHz and has done similar channel characterizations [RGB-13, SNS-14]. It is interesting to note that the channel properties reported by both these campaigns are broadly in-line (e.g., both report NLOS path loss exponents of 3.53/ 3.7 and NLOS propagation distances of around 200m).

Mid GHz range:

In the 31-41GHz frequency band, the 38GHz band is the most investigated due to the fixed point to multipoint services operating in this band. There is a quite large number of publications with channel measurements in the 38GHz band [RBM12], [RRE14], [RSM13], [XRB00]. The 38GHz frequency band has been investigated due to large bandwidth available [RRE14], [RSM13].

There are also experiments in the 41–51GHz region. In [SAA99] a mm-wave amplifier between 41 and 46 GHz was implemented and tested. The Communications Technology Laboratory of the NIST has developed a calibrated signal source for channel sounders at 44 GHz [NIST15]. A 16-element phased-array transmitter in the range 40-45GHz was also demonstrated in [KOH09]. Finally, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) conducted propagation measurements between air and ground in the range 43-47GHz for broadband wireless communications [ICAO14].

High GHz range:

Experiments in the E-band were conducted e.g. with the Huawei RTN 380 [HW13]. The trial has been carried out in UK. The aim of the trial was to investigate the performance of the E-Band technology. In addition, ITU-R propagation models have been also investigated by using the weather information retrieved during the trial.

Another demonstration is the 100+ Gbps transmission in the 71-76GHz and 81-86GHz bands at Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2014 [HW14]. This is a 5G prototype which utilized a novel transceiver architecture operating in the 70-90GHz spectrum band, as well as advanced transmission technologies, especially, multi-antenna pre-coding technology.

Nokia Networks demonstrated 5G speed of 10Gbps at 73GHz with National Instrument at the Brooklyn 5G Summit [N16]. The demonstration showed how massive MIMO and beam steering can be achieved with phased array technology at 73GHz, using a large number of antenna elements.

6.2 Existing mobile and some other co-primary allocations

In this section, the current ITU-R spectrum allocations for mobile services in the aforementioned frequency ranges are investigated. In most of the cases the mobile allocations are in a co-primary basis, meaning that there are other primary users for these bands as well. These other co-primary allocations are also identified. Many co-primary users are incumbent in these bands. The current allocation of the band is not necessary in line with the current usage or utilization of the same band. The legend of the figures provided in this section is as follows: in capital letters indicate a primary allocation, while in simple letters indicate a secondary allocation. It should be noted that the figures only capture the allocations of terrestrial mobile and fixed services and not the satellite services.

Besides the availability of spectrum, identifying contiguous bands is crucial. In particular, some of the envisaged 5G use cases require wider bandwidths as discussed in the paragraph below. On the other hand, having adjacent bands for each operator (or other service provider) would increase the economies of scale for manufacturing devices in these bands and hence would reduce the device costs. Therefore, for mobile operations, having globally or regionally harmonised adjacent bands would facilitate global roaming, even for devices supporting only a few of the future 5G bands. For these reasons, it is important to identify the availability of contiguous bands for 5G operations. For the use cases identified in section 4, an average bandwidth estimation was conducted, considering the likely data rates and aggregated cell/area throughputs as well as the foreseen improvements in spectrum efficiencies and cell densities by 2020. The ITU document [ITU13], looking at how these parameters will shape up by 2020, was used as a basis for these calculations. The average bandwidth requirements thus obtained are listed in Table 6-2.

Table 6-2 Bandwidth requirements for the use cases studied

Use case	BW-DL (MHz)	BW-UL (MHz)
Media on Demand	500	10
Cloud services (pico cell environment)	300	50
Dense urban society with distributed crowds	1175	2350
Smart office	1000	270
5G immersive experience	1640	820
50+Mbps everywhere	588	294
Moving Hotspots (Relay/cell in-vehicle)	100	50
Moving Hotspots (No in-vehicle cell/relay)	50000	25000
Remote surgery/ robotic control	500	10
Tactile internet	10	10

The table illustrates that many of the use cases that can be categorized as extreme mobile broadband (xMBB), require bandwidths of 500MHz or more. An interesting point can be noted about the moving hotspots, i.e. by having the in-vehicle cell/relay the bandwidth required for access can be drastically reduced. This is a reflection on the very good SINR levels (leading to higher spectral efficiencies) that can be achieved by in vehicle cells. However, having in-vehicle cells puts a lot of demands on the wireless backhaul links, which have not been addressed in the BW estimates here. The very low latency tactile internet type applications need relatively lower bandwidths. When ultra high reliability is added to this in the use cases of remote surgery/robotic control again the bandwidth requirements increase.

6.2.1 Low GHz (6-31GHz) range

According to ITU-R [ITU-R] the range 5.925-11.7GHz is divided into 32 sub-ranges in order to be allocated to different services such as fixed, fixed-satellite, mobile, space research, meteorological satellite, radiolocation, radio navigation, maritime radio navigation, aeronautical radio navigation, and earth exploration-satellite. Mobile is primarily allocated in the ranges 5.925-8.5GHz, 10-10.45GHz, 10.5-10.68GHz and 10.7-11.7GHz summing up to 4.2GHz of spectrum. Figure 5-1 shows details for mobile and other fixed allocations in the three regions between 6-11GHz. The most of the allocated spectrum has the same allocation in the 3 regions (except for the range 10-10.45GHz) and it is always allocated together with fixed links. The European common allocation level [ECR025] tries to follow the ITU-R1 mobile allocation with exception of the ranges 5.925-7.145GHz, 7.235-7.250GHz (total 1.235GHz) where mobile is replaced by earth exploration-satellite; 8.4-8.5GHz allocate radiolocation as secondary. On the contrary mobile has allocation at the European level at 10.45-10.5 but not at ITU-R1.

Figure 6-1 Mobile and Fixed allocations in the range 6-11GHz

In 5.925 and 8.5 GHz at least some ranges do not have mobile in the European common allocation according to CEPT table and if it does then sharing with military service and/or Earth exploration-satellite service (EESS) has to be taken into account. The range 7750-7900MHz (150MHz) is a harmonized band in all 3 regions with the CEPT allocations where sharing with meteorological-satellite (s/e) is expected.

The main use for the range between 8.5-9.9GHz is for radiolocation services and other type of radio navigation. In Europe the entire range is identified for major military utilization in the ECA. In some European countries the lower part 8.5-8.75GHz is allocated to Mobile and/or Fixed on a primary basis. The ranges 8.5-8.55GHz, 8.65-8.75GHz, 8.85-9GHz and 9.2-9.3GHz coexistence with Radiolocation, e.g., aeronautical navigation, need to be considered.

All the range 10.6-10.7GHz in Europe is primarily allocated to EESS and for radio astronomy with the main interest for the measurement of rain, snow, sea state, and ocean wind and soil moisture. This frequency range is used by passive sensors to study natural phenomena producing radio emissions at frequencies fixed by the laws of nature, and therefore shifting frequency to avoid or mitigate interference problems may not be possible.

The reference [ECC173] shows the development for fixed service in the point to point (P-P) link for Europe. The results of the questionnaire for 31 CEPT countries indicated 20242 links declared active in this range, which has been traditionally used for P-P links since a long time. Significant number of countries indicates a moderate trend to increase the usage of this range in the next years (10 to 30% increases), some report even a higher percentage, and some others indicate the band is congested or close to congestion.

The range 7.1-8.5 GHz trend for fixed shows that about 38500 P-P links have been declared active in this range, which is also a historical band for P-P applications. The frequency use in this band is not harmonized, due to the fact that its use has started quite a long time ago, with analogue systems, and many countries adopted national plans at that time, without coordination with other countries.

The range 8.5-8.75GHz is allocated to the fixed and mobile services on a primary basis for some countries. However, all the range from 8.5-9.9GHz is identified for major military utilization in CEPT countries.

According to ITU-R [ITURR] and FCC [FCC15], there are four primary mobile bands in 11-21GHz frequency range potentially usable for 5G:

Frequency (GHz)	Bandwidth (MHz)
10.5 – 11.7 GHz (excl. 10.68 – 10.7 GHz)	1180
12.75 – 13.25 GHz	500
14.4 – 15.35 GHz	950
17.8 – 19.7 GHz	1900

Table 6-3 Primary mobile band in 11-21GHz frequency range [ITURR]

Figure 6-2 reports a synthesis of such frequency ranges where mobile applications are primarily allocated under the same rules in the three ITU regions.

Figure 6-2 Mobile and Fixed allocations in the 11-21GHz

There are also other primary allocations in these bands which are detailed below:

- *Frequency range [10.5 – 11.7]GHz*
 10.5–10.55GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed services, plus radiolocation in region 2.
 10.55 –10.6GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed services.
 10.6–10.68GHz band is allocated worldwide for earth exploration-satellite, fixed, radio astronomy and space research services.
 10.7–11.7GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed and fixed-satellite services (under different conditions for this last).
- *Frequency range [12.75 – 13.25]GHz*
 This band is allocated worldwide for fixed and fixed-satellite services.
- *Frequency range [14.4 – 15.35]GHz*
 14.4–14.8GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed and fixed-satellite services under various rules considering the sub frequency range considered).
 14.8 – 15.35GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed services.
- *Frequency range [17.8 – 19.7]GHz*
 17.8 – 18.6GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed and fixed-satellite services.
 18.6 – 18.8GHz is allocated worldwide for fixed, fixed-satellite, earth exploration-satellite services, plus space-research in region 2.
 18.8 – 19.7GHz band is allocated worldwide for fixed and fixed-satellite services (under various rules depending on the sub frequency range considered).

In the upper-part of Low GHz range, there is a mobile allocation but it is in a co-primarily basis, and the main other co-primary user is Fixed Satellite Systems (FSS). The ITU_Region 1 (which includes Europe) allocation contains contiguous spectrum of 2.4GHz in the 21.2-23.6GHz range and a further 4.25GHz in the 25.25-29.5GHz range.

The main co-primary user is Fixed Satellite Systems (FSS). The Satellite Ka band (17.5GHz-31GHz) overlaps with this frequency segment and many satellite operations (fixed and mobile) have co-primary allocations in this band [OFCOM13].

The other main (commercial) allocation (in US) is the Local Multipoint Distribution System (LMDS) which is a fixed service used for last mile digital TV transmissions, as a fixed system.

In US the LMDS services mainly use the 28GHz and 31GHz bands. In Europe, parts of the 28GHz band are prioritized for fixed services, including FWA (fixed Wireless Access). In Europe, the 40GHz band was identified for Multimedia Wireless Systems (MWS). However this was not successfully assigned and now this band is liberalized to provide P-P (Point to Point) fixed services as well. These frequencies were allocated around year 2000, when there was a huge hype for LMDS services. But the popularity of LMDS services have recently weaned, so the possibility of spectrum re-farming in these bands cannot be discounted. The other non-commercial systems in this range are radio astronomy, meteorology and space research (a passive user).

The mobile and terrestrial fixed allocations in 21-31 GHz are shown in Figure 6-3.

Figure 6-3 Mobile and Fixed allocations in the 21-31GHz range

In terms of availability of contiguous spectrum in low GHz range, based on the co-primary mobile allocate in ITU-R1, there is 2.575GHz of contiguous allocation in the range 5.925-8.5 GHz, 0.450GHz in the range 10-10.45GHz, 0.180GHz in the range 10.5-10.68GHz and 1GHz bandwidth at 10.7-11.7GHz.

There is also 1180MHz bandwidth (from 10.5 to 11.7 GHz, excluding 10.68-10.7 GHz), 500MHz bandwidth (from 12.75 to 13.25 GHz), 950MHz bandwidth (from 14.4GHz to 15.35GHz) and 1.9GHz bandwidth (from 17.8GHz to 19.7GHz) available on a co-primary basis. There is 2.4GHz bandwidth (from 21.2GHz to 23.6GHz) and 4.25GHz bandwidth (from 25.25GHz to 29.5GHz) available on a co-primary basis.

6.2.2 Mid GHz (31-51GHz) range

There is mobile allocation in this range on a co-primarily basis. The ITU allocation in Europe for these frequency ranges up to 41GHz is shown in the Figure 6-4 and in Table 6-4. The mobile services has allocation in 31-31.3GHz bands and in the range of 36-40GHz. The frequency range from 36 to 40GHz is interesting for 5G systems due to the availability of large contiguous bandwidths. The other co-primary users in these frequency ranges are mainly Fixed and Satellite services (Fixed and Mobile) and Space Research. The 38GHz frequency range is popular especially for fixed digital point to multi-point services (LMDS). The allocation details for this frequency range are shown in Table 6-4.

Start Freq [GHz]	End Freq [GHz]	Bandwidth [GHz]	Primary Allocation(s)	Secondary Allocation(s)
31	31.3	0.3	Fixed / mobile	Space Research / Standard Frequency and Time Signal-Satellite (space-to-Earth)
31.3	31.5	0.2	Earth exploration-satellite (passive) / radio astronomy / space research (passive)	
31.5	31.8	0.3	Earth exploration-satellite (passive) / radio astronomy / space research (passive)	Fixed / Mobile except aeronautical mobile /
31.8	32	0.2	Fixed / radionavigation / space research (deep space) (space-to-earth)	
32	32.3	0.3	Fixed / radionavigation / space research (deep space) (space-to-earth)	
32.3	33	0.7	Fixed / inter-satellite / radionavigation	
33	33.4	0.4	Fixed / radionavigation	
33.4	34.2	0.8	Radiolocation	
34.2	34.7	0.5	Radiolocation / space research (deep space) (earth-to-space)	
34.7	35.2	0.5	Radiolocation	Space Research
35.2	35.5	0.3	Meteorological aids / radiolocation	
35.5	36	0.5	Earth exploration-satellite (active) / meteorological aids / radiolocation / space research (active)	
36	37	1	Earth exploration-satellite (passive) / fixed / mobile / space research (passive)	
37	37.5	0.5	Fixed / mobile except aeronautical mobile / space operation (space-to-earth)	

37.5	38	0.5	Fixed / fixed-satellite (space-to-earth) / mobile except aeronautical mobile / space research (space-to-earth)	Earth Exploration-Satellite (space-to-Earth)
38	39.5	1.5	Fixed / fixed-satellite (space-to-earth) / mobile	Earth Exploration-Satellite (space-to-Earth)
39.5	40	0.5	Fixed / fixed-satellite (space-to-earth) / mobile / mobile-satellite (space-to-earth)	Earth Exploration-Satellite (space-to-Earth)
40	40,5	0,5	Fixed / fixed-satellite (space-to-earth) / mobile / mobile-satellite (space-to-earth) / space research (earth-to-space)	Earth Exploration-Satellite (space-to-Earth)
40,5	41	0,5	Broadcasting / broadcasting-satellite / fixed	

Table 6-4 Allocation details for the frequency range 31-41GHz

The ITU-R allocations for this frequency range are illustrated in Fig. 6.4 below.

Figure 6-4 Mobile and Fixed allocations in the 31-41GHz range

With reference to the European ECO Frequency System [ECO], the range from 41 to 51GHz can be subdivided in Europe into 15 frequency allocations, for fixed satellite, broadcasting satellite, mobile, radio astronomy, radio navigation, and amateur usage.

The following bands in Table 6-5 can be identified in order to analyse potential usages for 5G:

Frequency (GHz)	Bandwidth (MHz)	Allocations	Applications
41 – 42	1000	Broadcasting, Fixed, Broadcasting-satellite	Fixed, FSS Earth Stations, MWS (Multimedia Wireless Systems)
42 – 42.5	500	Fixed,	MWS,

		Broadcasting, Broadcasting-satellite	Fixed, FSS Earth Stations
42.5 – 43.5	1000	Fixed, Fixed-Satellite (Earth-to-Space), Mobile except aeronautical mobile, Radio astronomy	Fixed, FSS Earth Stations, MWS, Radio astronomy
43.5 – 45.5	2000	Mobile-satellite, Mobile, Fixed-satellite	Defense systems
45.5 – 47	1500	Mobile-satellite, Radionavigation, Radionavigation-satellite, Mobile	-
47 – 47.2	200	Amateur, Amateur-satellite	Amateur, Amateur-satellite
47.2 – 47.5	300	Fixed-Satellite (Earth-to-Space), Fixed, Mobile	Feeder links, HAPS (High Altitude Platform Station), PMSE (Programme Making and Special Events), FSS Earth Stations
47.5 – 47.9	400	Mobile, Fixed-satellite (Space-to-Earth), Fixed-satellite (Earth-to-Space), Fixed	FSS Earth Stations, PMSE, Feeder links
47.9 – 48.2	300	Fixed, Fixed-satellite (Earth to Space), Mobile	Feeder links, HAPS, FSS Earth stations, PMSE
48.2 – 48.54	340	Mobile, Fixed-satellite (Earth-to-Space), Fixed-satellite (Space-to-Earth), Fixed	PMSE, Fixed, Feeder links, FSS Earth stations
48.54 – 49.44	900	Fixed, Fixed-satellite (Earth-to-Space), Mobile, Radio astronomy	FSS Earth stations, Feeder links, Radio astronomy, PMSE, Fixed
49.44 – 50.2	760	Mobile, Fixed-satellite (Earth-to-Space), Fixed-satellite (Space-to-Earth), Fixed	FSS Earth stations, Fixed, PMSE
50.2 – 50.4	200	Earth exploration-satellite (passive), Space research (passive)	Passive sensors (satellite), Radio astronomy
50.4 – 51.4	1000	Mobile-satellite (Earth-to-space),	Fixed

		Fixed, Fixed-satellite	
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Table 6-5 Allocation details for the frequency range 41-51GHz

A synthesis of the availability of mobile allocations in these bands can be graphically depicted in the following Figure 6-5 for 41-51 GHz range, where it is clear that there are a lot of mobile allocations for ITU Region 1 (small differences can be observed with respect to Europe as Region 1 covers also Africa and part of Middle East). Note also that can be merged into bigger contiguous chunks of spectrum.

Figure 6-5 Mobile and Fixed allocations in the 41-51GHz range

From the previous chart it is clear that there are other primary allocations in these bands:

- 41-42GHz: allocated for broadcasting and fixed services. No primary allocation exists for mobile.
- 42-42.5GHz: same as the previous band, no allocation for mobile.
- 42.5-43.5GHz: fixed, fixed satellite, radio astronomy, and mobile (except aeronautical mobile) allocations. Currently this band does not have mobile allocation.
- 43.5-45.5GHz: mobile-satellite, fixed-satellite, and mobile allocations. Currently, used by defense systems. Although having mobile allocations, this band is an EU harmonized military band dedicated for satellite UL and mobile military services.
- 45.5-47GHz: radio navigation, mobile-satellite, and mobile allocations. It is one of the least used bands currently in Europe, so it may be of interest for mobile allocation in 5G.
- 47-47.2GHz: it is reserved for amateur usage. Can be of interest for 5G mobile but it will require allocation.
- 47.2-50.2GHz: this region is split into several subbands in ITU-R, with the same primary allocations (mobile, fixed, fixed satellite and radio astronomy). It is of interest for 5G mobile allocations in the region 41 – 50 GHz.
- 50.2-50.4GHz: it is reserved for Earth exploration and space research, therefore of little interest for 5G mobile allocations.

- 50.4–51.4GHz: mobile-satellite, fixed and fixed-satellite allocations (no mobile allocations). Currently used for fixed applications.

In terms of availability of contiguous spectrum in Mid GHz range, there is 1GHz bandwidth (from 36GHz to 37GHz) and 1.5GHz bandwidth (from 38GHz to 39.5GHz) available on a co-primary basis.

There is 1GHz bandwidth (from 41GHz to 42GHz), 1GHz bandwidth (from 42.5GHz to 43.5GHz), 2GHz (from 43.5GHz to 45.5GHz), 1.5GHz (from 45.5GHz to 47GHz), and 3GHz (from 47.2GHz to 50.2GHz) available on a co-primary basis. These ranges can be added to get wider bandwidths.

6.2.3 High GHz (70-100GHz) range

There is mobile allocation in this band but this is in a co-primarily basis. The main co-primary user is Fixed Service in E-band as shown in Figure 6-6. Since 2000, regulators have made available high frequency bands at 71-76GHz and 81-86GHz, which are generally known as "E-band". E-band enables gigabit-per-second data rates also because of huge amount of available spectrum (10GHz).

According to channel measurements, the Path Loss Exponent (PLE) of E-band is similar to the Ka-Band. It is expected that E-band can cover a range between 50m-100m even in NLOS scenarios.

- Existing fixed links in the E-Band are typically deployed at height and above local clutter (typ. > 25m) to achieve maximum range and line-of-sight propagation. These fixed links also use high-gain antennas with very highly-directional (0.5°-3° beam width) beams
- IMT in the E-band will be for high-capacity small cells, with base stations deployed below roof top (typ. <10 m). These will use antenna arrays (e.g., 32×32) to create large numbers of directional (3°-6° beam width) beams with down tilts of typically 10° or more.

Calculations indicate that, for typical deployment geometries, and cautious parameters and protection criteria, the protection distances between IMT base stations and fixed link receivers can be 10 to 100 meters depending on the frequency adjacency as in Figure 6-7.

Figure 6-6 Mobile and Fixed allocations in the 71-100GHz range

Figure 6-7 Illustration of possible co-existence of Fixed and IMT systems

In terms of availability of contiguous spectrum in High GHz range, there is 5GHz bandwidth (from 71GHz to 76GHz) and 5GHz bandwidth (from 81GHz to 86GHz) available on a co-primary basis. The figures 6-8 and 6-9 indicate that in general in higher carrier frequencies, there is wider bandwidth available for mobile allocation. Notice that the merging of adjacent band is not considered in the distribution but it is important to consider it as a solution when allocating spectrum.

Figure 6-8 Bandwidth distribution (6-100GHz range) for Mobile allocation

Figure 6-9 Bandwidth distribution (6-100GHz range) for Mobile allocation

6.3 Availability of technology components

Another important front is the availability of chipsets, Radio Frequency components, antenna arrays, (at least on a prototype basis) that will be discussed in the section. Such availability is an indication of the technology readiness for a frequency range for mobile operations.

In the 6-11GHz ranges there is no cellular mobile network deployed, thus no technology component has been developed for this purpose. However, we can learn from the MINI-LINK point to point products (in Ericsson) which are available for the range 5.9 to 8.5GHz. The band 8.5 to 10.5GHz is a dedicated radar band so there are no communication products there. The MINI-LINK system has radio and antennas for outdoor uses, modems and switches for indoor. All the microwave parts are outdoors. Thus it is possible to find MMIC for Radio chains, Power amplifiers, LNA's, mixers, filters and other RF components for these bands. However, most bands offer low volume of components (except for 7.093-7.897GHz and 7.731-8.467GHz), as a consequence the integration level is low and the cost usually high/higher.

In general, it can be argued that components exist but a lot of discrete MMICs need to be used to form an RF line-up. This implies that it is feasible to build demo/prototype systems (or low production volume systems) yet they will be both bulky and costly. In order to build a competitive solution, more custom type solutions need to be built, including new integrated MMICs and that will take time (including design, verification and qualification can take about 2 years).

Ericsson made a demonstration, jointly with NTT DoCoMo, at MWC 2015 of a system operating in the 15GHz band. They reached a peak data rate of 5.250Gbps. As depicted in Figure 6-10, such testbed should fit indoor and outdoor installations and multi-site deployments.

Figure 6-10 Ericsson testbed at 15GHz

The RF components for upper Low GHz range band have been developed by Samsung on a proto-type basis to conduct their 28GHz trials as shown in Figure 6-11. Similarly adaptive antenna systems and beam-forming algorithms/ components have been developed both by Samsung and NYU. Considering the commercial availability of satellite and LMDS system wireless components in this band, it will not be a huge challenge to produce mobile cellular components in this frequency range.

World's mmWave Testbed and High Speed Mobility Test

1.2 Gbps (2013) → 7.5 Gbps (2014)

1.2 Gbps at 110 km/h (2014)

Figure 6-11 Samsung testbed at 28 GHz

The RF components for upper Low GHz range band have been developed by Samsung on a prototype basis to conduct their 28GHz trials as shown in Figure 6-11.

There exist products in the market for 38 GHz point to multi-point systems. Therefore in the context of technologies for RF components and antennas this frequency range is well explored. There are prototypes designed to conduct measurements and experiments in this frequency region. There is no clear information of already available products in the market, although this could change as a response to the growing demand for experiments and trials from the Industry.

There are already a number of RF components and chips available for the E-band. Examples include the 40-nm CMOS direct transmitter [ZR14] and the E-band Doherty power amplifier

[KZR14] by KU Leuven, the Toshiba 90nm CMOS transceiver at 77GHz [MOH10], and the SMT-ready E-band radio frontends by Infineon [INF14,INF15]. Furthermore, Huawei has conducted multiple demonstrations on E-band transmissions. One demonstration is the E-band trial with the Huawei RTN 380 [HW13].

The demo detailed in [HW14] is a 5G prototype which utilized a novel transceiver architecture operating on the 70-90GHz spectrum band, as well as advanced transmission technologies, especially, multi-antenna precoding technology. The prototype demonstrated that it could overcome out-of-band emission leakage for flexible spectrum utilization, while also reducing peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) for improved energy efficiency, which allows for longer terminal battery life.

6.4 Assessment of Spectrum Suitability on KPIs

There is on-going discussion about the suitability of mm-wave spectrum (or certain parts of it) for mobile deployments. In this section we will assess the suitability of mm-wave spectrum on 4 key KPIs related to mobile communications, i.e. coverage, capacity, mobility and device complexity. It should be noted that due to time limitations, this analysis is conducted only for outdoor or outdoor to indoor, homogeneous mm-wave networks. Yet it is highly relevant to consider heterogeneous networks with lower frequency anchor cells. The reader is referred to [LNW+13] and references there-in, for some analysis on coverage limitations in such deployments.

There are multiple parameters which can influence the performance of potential mobile communication systems in mm-wave spectrum. As noted earlier, one of the main benefit in mm-wave frequency range is the availability of very wide bandwidths. This can potentially compensate the negative impacts of excessive path loss in these frequencies as long as the system is coverage limited. This is particularly true in higher GHz frequencies, where the path loss is more severe, yet there are very wide bandwidths available. By increasing the number of antenna elements for higher beam-forming gain, the path loss can be countered as well. As the spacing of antenna elements gets physically smaller in higher frequencies, this antenna increment can be achieved without a significant increase in the array sizes. As with cellular systems in any other band, the cell sizes can also be adjusted to provide the targeted coverage and capacity.

Due to the complex interactions of these multiple parameters, we conducted this analysis as two strands. Some of the parameters will be fixed in each strand and this makes their impact across the frequency range fixed as well, allowing the impact of other parameters across the frequency range to be analysed with more clarity. The two strands will be applied across all 4 KPIs, so a clearer comparison on the parameter impacts on each KPI can be obtained. Both the analyses are meant to be comparative studies, i.e. we study the relative impact of increasing carrier frequency has on these selected KPIs as compared to carrier frequency at 6GHz. Thus $f_{ref}=6GHz$ for this study. The two strands can be listed as follows;

- Strand 1: Fix the system bandwidth to around 500MHz and study the impact of incrementing number of antenna elements. As 2 KPIs are assessed through multi-parameter simulations, we cannot fix the bandwidth to exactly 500MHz. The antenna element numbers will be incremented in line with $\left(\frac{f_c}{f_{ref}}\right)^2$ to counter for the incrementing path loss. Here f_c is the carrier frequency under consideration.
- Strand 2: Fix the number of antenna elements ($N_{ant}=32$) across the frequency range and study the impact of incrementing the system bandwidth. The bandwidth is incremented in line with the values obtained from the coverage KPI analysis.

Two of the KPIs, coverage and capacity, are assessed with the aid of multi-cell simulations. The other 2 (mobility and device complexity) analyses are based on theoretical quantitative analysis

on some related parameters. Due to the multi-dimensional nature of the simulations, they take up a lot of time and computing resources and hence the coverage and capacity analyses are limited to spot values in some of the parameters.

To simplify the quantification of the assessments, we derive a suitability value in the range of [0 10] for each of the KPIs. As we are using 6GHz as the reference point (the starting point of the mm-wave spectrum of interest for the mmMAGIC project), the suitability value for all KPIs at this reference would be 10.

6.4.1 Coverage KPI

The coverage KPI in this study is assessed in terms of the cell sizes needed to achieve a certain cell edge data rate. The cell radii are changed in step sizes so this is a rough estimate, yet the relative changes across the frequency range indicate the trends we are looking for. We run multi-cell simulations with multiple users and build up a data set on the data rates achieved by the cell edge users, in light of the path loss and shadowing of the signal (S), noise accumulated (N) and the interference (I) from the other users. The cell-edge data rate (R_{CE}) is calculated using the fundamental Shannon equation as follows

$$R_{CE} = B * \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{S}{N + I} \right)$$

where the additional term B is the bandwidth occupied by each user. The cell edge data rates for multiple users are captured and the 95th percentile of the cdf (cumulative distribution function) is taken as the representative data rate.

The noise power is considered to be additive white Gaussian and proportionally incremented with the bandwidth ($N=kTB$, with k =Boltzman constant and T =temperature in Kelvin units). The signal power is derived from the following relationship

$$S = P + G_{BF} - PL$$

where P is the transmit power, G_{BF} is the cumulative antenna gains (transmitter and receiver sides) and PL is the path loss. The path loss is a critical factor here and reliable models are still emerging for this mm-wave frequency range, for cellular applications. We utilize the recent path loss models from NYU (work by Rappaport et.al.) [RMS+15], where they propose path loss models derived from extensive measurements for the 28GHz, 38GHz and 73GHz carrier frequencies, in urban environments. The simulations need fixed, spot carrier frequencies and we select the above 3 frequencies covering the low, mid and high GHz ranges. Additionally, we select the $f_{ref}=6$ GHz as the reference simulation and use the WINNER II path loss model [WIN07] for this frequency.

The bench mark for coverage analysis is set at achieving 100Mbps data rate at the cell edge and it is statistically analysed with data rates achieved by multiple cell edge users. The cells are assumed to be outdoor cells, with a shadowing component included in the Path Loss models.

Coverage KPI – Strand 1 assessment:

As noted above, in this strand we fix the bandwidth and study the number of cells needed to provide the 100Mbps cell edge data rate. The antenna numbers are incremented as with the

$\left(\frac{f_c}{f_{ref}} \right)^2$ ratio. The antennas are used in purely beamforming mode, to mitigate the path loss.

It does bring an additional benefit of reduced interference at the cell edge, as the wanted signal and the interferences are unlikely to impact the same narrower area of the beams. However this gain is only partial, as we consider only one cell edge user per cell. The simulations however need the antenna numbers (n) to be a power of 2. The lowest carrier frequency applicable in the simulations with $n=4$ is 10GHz, so we use it as a shifted reference value in this work. The simulations are run for multiple bandwidth values in the range of 500-600MHz. The results summary for this analysis is listed below in Table 6-6.

Carrier frq (GHz)	10	28	38	73
Number of Antenna Elements	4	32	64	256
BW (MHz)	500	500	500	600
Cell radius (m)	250 (R_{ref})	250	250	100
Coverage - No. of cells (R_{ref}/R) ²	1	1	1	6.25
Suitability value	10	10	10	1.6

Table 6-6 Coverage KPI analysis – Strand 1

The simulation results indicate that up to the mid GHz range in the mm-wave spectrum, the path loss can be effectively compensated by the increment in the antenna numbers, roughly at the rate of square of the frequency increment. There are other factors considered in the simulator and the path loss models, like the increasing probability of shadowing when the beams get narrower. These effects make the cell sizes much smaller for the 73GHz carrier to achieve the 100Mbps cell edge data rate. Note that the bandwidth indicated here is 600MHz, as majority of the simulations returned 600MHz (in step sizes of 50MHz) bandwidth for cell size to achieve this data rate. Some simulations returned 500MHz, but as a majority representation, we have indicated 600MHz bandwidth. The quantification of suitability is done w.r.t the number of cells required to cover a unit area, with reference to the cell sizes at 10 GHz.

Coverage KPI – Strand 2 assessment:

In strand 2 of coverage assessment, we fix the number of antennas to 32 across the frequency range and analyse the cell sizes needed to achieve the 100Mbps cell edge data rate, while also changing the bandwidth. The 32 antenna number is an arbitrary value, to suit the mid frequency range, hence the absolute bandwidth values obtained from the analysis should also be treated as arbitrary. However the relative change of these values (w.r.t. the reference) does carry significance, as parameters across multiple simulations have been kept constant.

In interpreting simulation results, we have looked to minimize the cell radius, while allowing the bandwidth increment. However, when moving onto higher frequencies, only similar or higher bandwidths to the lower spot frequencies were considered, to be in line with the general trend of larger bandwidth availability for higher carrier frequencies. The results are reported in Table 6-7 below.

Carrier Freq (GHz)	6	28	38	73
BW (MHz)	400	400	500	1400
Cell radius (m)	200 (R_{ref})	150	100	50
Coverage - No. of cells (R_{ref}/R) ²	1	1.77	4	16
Suitability value	10	5.625	2.5	0.0625

Table 6-7 Coverage KPI analysis-Strand 2

The results indicate that the bandwidth expansion is not as effective as the expansion in the number of antennas to combat loss of coverage. The cell sizes successively become smaller and hence the number of cells required to achieve coverage in a unit area increases. We have quantified the suitability value for this strand 2 accordingly. However it should be noted that the cell sizes were changed in steps of 50m, so the suitability value should be treated as a rough indication of the trends across the frequency ranges.

6.4.2 Capacity KPI

The capacity KPI is also assessed with the aid of multi-cell simulations. As with the coverage analysis, only spot values are available in certain parameters, due to the complexity and the

time consumption in the simulations. The simulations address certain specific conditions, as outlined below.

In this scenario the macro base station will be serving indoor users, from a rooftop of an adjacent building. The outdoor to indoor propagation model considers free space path loss, diffraction loss, indoor loss and body loss.

Figure 6-12 Specific scenario addressed in capacity KPI

Methodology

For the outdoor to indoor case, the average data rate is computed from the users that are indoor in the border of the cell range, but the indoor depth of the user is vary from 0.5 to 10 meters.

Figure 6-13 Users considered for average data rate

For one experiment the bandwidth is assumed to be constant at 100MHz . The directivity of the transmission enables less interference between the links. In the outdoor network in mm-wave bands, the highly directional links can be modelled as “pseudo-wired”. As a first assumption, we then consider negligible the inter cell interference between non-adjacent links [ISM+14, ZZ+14, MSM09]. In mm-wave systems the thermal noise dominates interference: highly directional transmissions used in mm-wave systems combined with short cell radii result in links that are in relatively high SINR with little interference [ALS+13]. As a first assumption we then can assume that there is no intra-cell interference.

In order to model different environments for the end user, we have considered 2 different cases: Case1 where a user is in good propagation conditions (i.e. lower building penetration loss); and Case2 where a user is in tougher propagation conditions (i.e. higher building penetration loss). We utilize results from Case1 in this capacity analysis.

Then the received signal power (P_{Rx}) can be computed as follows. The EIRP is the effective Isotropic Radiated Power. G_{Rx} is the Antenna gain at the receiver and PL is the propagation losses.

$$P_{Rx} = EIRP + G_{Rx} - PL$$

The average data rate is dependent on

$$DataRate_{Avr} = \left[\rho BW \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{Rx}{Noise} \right) \right]_{Avr}$$

Where ρ is the the fraction of the BW resource allocated per eac user. The area capacity is computed as follows. The UEs refer to the number of active user equipment (or active users) per cell and the cells refer to the number of cells per km^2 area.

$$Area\ Capacity = \left(\frac{cells}{km^2} \right) * \left(\frac{Ues}{cell} \right) * DataRate_{Avr}$$

A particular feature that was considered in the capacity analysis is that the number of antennas cannot increase infinitely. Regarding antenna assumption, the area (A) of the antenna is assumed to be $1 \times 0.1\ m^2$, and it is kept constant for all frequencies. However, the antenna gain is computed as (where c is the speed of light)

$$G = 4\pi(f_{GHz})^2 / c^2$$

This means that the antenna gain will increase with frequency by keeping the same antenna area. However, it is not realistic to assume infinite increment of gain, thus a maximum 50dBi transmitter/ receiver combine beamforming gain is considered. The antenna gain is a direct function of the size of the antenna (in wavelengths). In the same physical area but when the frequency is doubled, 4 times higher antenna gain (6 dB) is produced. In principle, the number of elements is the area divided by $(\lambda/2)^2$, where λ is the wavelength. In other words, the number of elements that could be fit into a certain area with $\lambda/2$ spacing between the elements, define the antenna gain.

The antenna gain variation across the carrier frequency range is shown below.

Figure 6-14 Antenna gain variations considered in the capacity KPI analysis

This antenna gain consideration puts some restrictions in the way the capacity KPI can be analysed in strand 1 and 2. The strand 1, where the number of antenna elements (and hence the antenna gain) increment with the carrier frequency, can be only analysed for 6-20 GHz frequency range. Similarly for strand 2, where the antenna gain is constant, only the frequency range 20-100 GHz can be employed for the analysis.

Capacity KPI – Strand 1 assessment:

The capacity assessment takes the area capacity values generated by the simulations for the 6-20GHz range, where the antenna gains show increment. The system bandwidth is fixed to 500MHz and the inter site distance (ISD) to 300m. These fixed values resemble similar trends for the coverage analysis (strand 1) in Table 6-8.

Carrier frequency (GHz)	6 (f_{ref})	10	20
Area capacity (Gbps/km ²)	297	284	185
Normalized to f_{ref}	1	0.95	0.62
Suitability value	10	9.5	6.2

Table 6-8 Capacity KPI analysis – Strand 1

The capacity values are normalized to the starting frequency (6 GHz) and scaled in the range of [0 10]. The results indicate that the capacity KPI show a gradual decrement as per the incrementing carrier frequency. This is in line with the findings that coverage can be largely maintained with the higher number of antennas in this frequency range. Conversely, the capacity KPI can be maintained with increasing the number of cells gradually in this range, but it will then impact the coverage KPI. These trends further show the inter-relationships amongst the KPIs.

Capacity KPI – Strand 2 assessment:

For the strand 2, the antenna gains are fixed and the BW and cell sizes are varied in order to achieve capacity. The capacity simulation results were provided for ISD=200m and 300m and for system bandwidths of 500MHz and 1GHz. We had to do some interpolations to bring these bandwidth values in-line with the values reported in Table 6-7, so that the baseline parameters are aligned as much as possible. The resulting capacity values are presented in Table 6-9 below. The cell radius and the bandwidth values have been aligned with the coverage KPI analysis.

Carrier frq (GHz)	20 (f_{ref})	28	38	73
System BW (MHz)	400	400	500	1400
Cell radius (m)	150	150	100	50
Area capacity (Gbps/km ²)	212	121	182	84
Normalized to f_{ref}	1	0.57	0.86	0.40
Suitability value	10	5.71	8.58	3.96

Table 6-9 Capacity KPI analysis – Strand 2

As the simulation conditions make 20GHz the starting frequency for this analysis, we normalize the achieved area capacity values at this point and derive the suitability scaling. The values degrade gradually in the mid GHz range and then sharply in the High GHz range. This is despite compensating for the wider bandwidths and the smaller cell sizes available in the high GHz range. There is a slight anomaly that the capacity values have increased from 28GHz to 38GHz,

but this can be attributed to the coarse step changes in cell sizes (150m to 100m) as needed in coverage KPI analysis. This highlights some limitations in the study, which we will capture in section 5.4.5.

6.4.3 Mobility KPI

In this analysis, assessment of the suitability of any available frequencies from 6 to 100 GHz is performed in terms of mobility support. The analysis excludes any considerations about regulatory conditions, emission limits, eventual presence of incumbents, etc. that could distort the purely technical discussion. In what follows it will be assumed that all bands are ideally available for use in 5G cellular communications.

In addition, further simplification will be assumed regarding antenna implementations. Both transmitter and receiver chains will in general comprise suitable antenna arrays to overcome increased path loss by means of beamforming. Any differences in antenna implementation, RF hardware, transceiver impairments, etc. across frequency will be skipped to keep the analysis as simple as possible, letting such considerations be part of the device complexity KPI. Some basic control mechanisms (like system broadcast) are intended to operate without beamforming, targeting the whole coverage area (at least in standalone deployments), and therefore the individual antennas should not have very directive patterns. Consequently, antennas with ideally constant radiation pattern across frequency will be considered. The effect of increased path loss will have to be compensated only by means of appropriate beamforming at both TX and RX ends.

In what follows the two strands described in Section 6.4 are analyzed for mobility assessment across frequency

Both strands require proper evaluation of the impact of frequency on mobility. Three phenomena are identified that may have significant impact on mobility: tracking accuracy, Doppler spread, and channel coherence time. The dependence with frequency of these three effects is separately analyzed; an overall figure of merit is then obtained that provides the suitability of frequencies between 6 and 100GHz in terms of mobility support; and application to the above two strands is highlighted in practical terms.

Impact of tracking accuracy

Free-space attenuation increases with frequency following the quadratic dependency $20\log(f)$, therefore beamforming gain will have to follow the same dependency with frequency. Gains in planar arrays are proportional to the product of the number of antennas in the H and V directions (N_H and N_V respectively), thus $G_{bf} \sim 10\log(N_H N_V)$. If the start and end frequencies under analysis are denoted by f_{min} and f_{max} respectively, and to ideally overcome the increased path loss, the following relation must be fulfilled

$$20\log\frac{f_{max}}{f_{min}} = 10\log\frac{(N_H N_V)_{max}}{(N_H N_V)_{min}}$$

As an example, going from 10 GHz to 100 GHz represents 20 dB increase in path loss, therefore the total number of antennas will have to grow by a factor 100x (or 10x in each H, V directions). Increased beamforming gain has a negative impact on device mobility, as the resulting beamwidth decreases accordingly which makes it more challenging to track the users. Neglecting the effect of the individual radiation patterns, the half-power beamwidth (HPBW) at the H and V planes is inversely proportional to the corresponding number of antennas:

$$\theta_{3dB,H} \cong \frac{k}{N_H}, \theta_{3dB,V} \cong \frac{k}{N_V}$$

If the users are concentrated in the same V plane then the tracking accuracy would only depend on the horizontal HPBW. However it is unlikely that users remain in the same V plane if hotspots with reduced dimensions are targeted, where the distances between users and antennas can

be small. If we define (for simplicity) the tracking accuracy (TA) as the product of the half-power beamwidths in H and V, we have

$$TA = \theta_{3dB,H} \cdot \theta_{3dB,V} \sim \frac{k'}{N_H N_V}$$

As a result, the relation between the defined tracking accuracy at the maximum and minimum frequencies of analysis will be given by

$$\frac{(TA)_{max}}{(TA)_{min}} = \frac{(N_H N_V)_{max}}{(N_H N_V)_{min}} = \left(\frac{f_{max}}{f_{min}}\right)^2$$

In this case, 100GHz is 100 times worse than 10GHz in terms of tracking accuracy.

It has to be emphasized that the above analysis considers antennas with ideally constant patterns, which may be somewhat unrealistic but anyway needed if a given sector coverage for broadcast control is to be maintained without beamforming.

Impact of Doppler spread

Another factor that gets strong importance at higher frequencies is the Doppler spread f_D , defined as

$$f_D = f_c \frac{v}{c}$$

where f_c is the carrier frequency, v is the user speed and c is the speed of light. To keep the analysis simple, we assume that the major scatterers for the received signal are within the beam area, even for the narrower beams. Thus the multi-path impacts causing the Doppler spread would still be seen even in narrower beams.

Therefore,

$$\frac{(f_D)_{max}}{(f_D)_{min}} = \frac{f_{max}}{f_{min}}$$

However, the real effects of Doppler spread in multicarrier systems (like OFDM and its variants) depends on the subcarrier width, which could scale with frequency so as to make the system robust to Doppler shifts even at very high frequencies. If this is the case then it would be complicated to assess the real effects of Doppler spread on the system.

Increasing the subcarrier width in multicarrier systems has the positive effect of reducing symbol length, but this of course has deep implications on the resulting numerology, which is unlikely to be allowed to change as flexibly as desired. One possible way forward could be to envisage a number of discrete alternatives for the numerology, preferably observing submultiple relationships, at targeted frequency points. Robustness to Doppler spread would then be maintained at those discrete frequencies.

Impact of channel coherence time

There is an additional negative effect linked to Doppler spread, namely the channel coherence time T_c , which follows the inverse relation $T_c \sim 1/f_D$. A shorter coherence time with frequency translates into poorer ability of the system to track channel variations (through link adaptation mechanisms and/or retransmissions). Linear dependency with frequency can therefore be stated also for T_c :

$$\frac{(T_c)_{max}}{(T_c)_{min}} = \frac{f_{max}}{f_{min}}$$

Overall figure of merit

The combination of the above three elements could lead to the definition of a figure of merit (e.g. between 0 and 10) that represents the inherent support of mobility at the different frequencies.

The impact of frequency on tracking accuracy could be assessed by taking the logarithm of the above defined tracking accuracy, thus leading to a linear dependency with frequency of the type

$$Mark_{TA} = MarkRef_{TA} - m_{TA} \cdot \log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)^2$$

where $Mark_{TA}$ denotes the mark related to tracking accuracy, f_{ref} represents an arbitrary reference frequency, $MarkRef_{TA}$ is the corresponding reference mark, and m_{TA} is a proportionality constant.

Regarding Doppler spread and channel coherence time, either if we consider scalable subcarrier widths or not, their individual effects would lead to the same type of linear dependency with frequency as tracking accuracy has (in the log domain)

$$Mark_D = MarkRef_D - m_D \cdot \log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)$$

$$Mark_{Coh} = MarkRef_{Coh} - m_{Coh} \cdot \log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)$$

Absorbing the different factors and constants we would then have an overall linear dependency of the mark in the log domain as follows:

$$Mark = Mark_{TA} + Mark_D + Mark_{Coh} = MarkRef - m \cdot \log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)$$

where $m \equiv 2m_{TA} + m_D + m_{Coh}$. The factor 2 accounts for the quadratic dependence of tracking accuracy with frequency. In case of considering ideally scalable subcarrier widths, m_D would equate to zero thus making the system insensitive to Doppler spread. As noted above, perhaps practical systems could only afford this at spot frequencies and dependence of the mark would still be linear out of those points.

The two combined parameters $MarkRef$ and m can be adjusted so as to reflect the relative differences in mobility support across different frequencies.

With regard to assigning values for the coefficients, the assignment of m_{TA} , m_D and m_{Coh} is somewhat arbitrary, but so is any absolute figure of merit for a given frequency, i.e. only the relative variations make sense when comparing different frequencies. According to recent experiments, it was proved that high frequencies can indeed be exploited even at high speeds, as successful field trials were conducted at 28 GHz by Samsung reaching 1.2 Gbps with 100 km/h mobility [SAM14]. Nokia and DoCoMo are also planning to extend their current 70 GHz indoor trials to outdoors, initially with pedestrian mobility [DCM15]. These facts suggest that suitability figures of around 3-4 could be assigned to 70 GHz. One possible factor to consider is the relative novelty of the problem to the mobile communications area. The Doppler factor and the limitations in channel coherence time are issues that have been around since the inception of mobile industry. The technologies to mitigate these problems are hence quite mature. While the beam tracking problem is quite novel to the industry, as even in 4G, most of the coverage provided is with 3-sector or even omni-directional cells. Thus beam tracking issue can be considered as more challenging to the industry.

Reflecting the above facts, we propose to induce the double the value of m_D and m_{Coh} to m_{TA} . The suggested values are $m_{TA}=2$ and m_D and $m_{Coh} = 1$.

Application of the figure of merit for the strand 1 assessment

Strand 1 considers the practical case of a variable number of antennas and fixed bandwidth. The figure of merit obtained above can be thus applied in its most general form, with all the three mentioned effects: tracking accuracy, Doppler spread, and channel coherence time. Their combined effects can be absorbed into suitable parameters $MarkRef|_{BW}$ and $m|_{BW}$ that should be adjusted to reflect mobility support across frequency:

$$Mark = MarkRef|_{BW} - m|_{BW} \cdot \log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)$$

where $m|_{BW} \equiv 2m_{TA} + m_D + m_{Coh}$.

With the assigned values as stated above, the combined value $m|_{BW}=6$ is applied for strand 1. $MarkRef|_{BW}$ is taken as maximum value (i.e., 10), so at the reference frequency (6 GHz), the suitability is scaled to 10. Although continuous values could be obtained for suitability on mobility, we only depict the spot frequency values as in line with the other KPIs.

Carrier frequency (GHz)	6 (f_{ref})	28	38	73
Suitability value	10	5.99	5.19	3.49

Table 6-10 Mobility KPI analysis – Strand 1

As the derived relationship is negative log-linear with the increasing of the frequency, the suitability factor degrades accordingly. As can be seen, the suitability decreases with frequency with a stronger variation in the range 6-28GHz. This is in line with the relatively high value of $m|_{BW}$ as per the combined effects of tracking accuracy, Doppler spread, and channel coherence time. This suggests that, in order to overcome mobility impairments at higher frequencies, emphasis should be on the range from 6 to 30GHz because impairments related with mobility will be strongly perceived at those frequencies. In this study, we have given higher emphasis on the relatively new challenge of beam alignment, but as the mm-wave mobile technologies mature, this would be better addressed. So this 'relative' mobility suitability values (relative across the frequency range) should be considered as an indication based on today's technology readiness.

Application of the figure of merit for the Strand 2 assessment

Strand 2 lets the bandwidth change with frequency while the number of antennas is kept fixed (e.g., 32). Tracking accuracy is therefore constant with frequency and the only effects are Doppler spread and channel coherence time, which lead to a similar linear dependence

$$Mark = MarkRef|_{no.antennas} - m|_{no.antennas} \cdot \log\left(\frac{f}{f_{ref}}\right)$$

where in this case $m|_{no.antennas} \equiv m_D + m_{Coh}$. The bandwidth itself has no effect on mobility, but the implicit frequency variations will impact mobility through the two above mentioned effects.

With the assigned co-efficient values, the combined co-efficient $m|_{no.antennas}=2$, for strand 2.

Carrier frequency (GHz)	6 (f_{ref})	28	38	73
Suitability value	10	8.66	8.4	7.83

Table 6-11 Mobility KPI analysis – Strand 2

Again the suitability values show decrement as per the negative log-linear relationship derived. Similar to the Strand 1 case, the suitability decreases with frequency although at a slower pace (in line with the lower value of $m|_{BW}$). Besides, the impact of increased Doppler spread and decreased coherence time with frequency is already well known in current state of the art, and overcoming it can be considered less challenging than addressing beam tracking issues. These values should thus be compared more with the values in Table 5-5 in terms of today's technology readiness. Strand 1 analysis can thus be highlighted as the most challenging scenario for mobility KPI assessments.

6.4.4 Device Complexity KPI

Device complexity is quite a complicated, yet an essential parameter to include in this analysis. By nature it covers a wide variety of technical issues, such as the hardware complexities brought on by multiple RF chains, the linearity issues with wider BW, the coupling/leakage issues with antenna elements, the algorithm complexities or the power consumption issues. We used simplistic analysis by considering only one parameter in the strand 1 and 2 analyses.

Device complexity KPI – Strand 1 assessment:

In order to provide quantitative indication for this KPI, we analysed computational complexity of digital beamforming algorithm. For the strand 1, we increase the number of antennas with the incrementing frequency, so we focus on the increasing digital beamforming computational complexity while supporting multiple antenna elements. It should be noted that in practical implementations, for mm-wave frequencies, analogue and hybrid beamforming techniques are used instead of digital beamforming which is a reasonable choice for sub mm-wave frequency bands.

This analysis is based on the eigen-beamforming scheme described in [Lee12] which take into account low rank channel matrices. The complexity is around $O\{N_T \cdot M^2\}$ in terms of complex multiplications, where N_T is the number of Tx antenna and M is the number of Rx antennas. There is always the possibility of utilizing Analogue beamforming when this complexity is higher, but with the cost of some limitations to beamforming.

Our analysis approach is that we fix the BW (reasonable value 500-600 MHz), but vary the antennas as $\left(\frac{f_c}{f_{ref}}\right)^2$ times the antenna elements number of the reference frequency f_{ref} , which is 10 GHz (shifted slightly from 6 GHz), for which we assume 4 antenna elements at the AP. We assume that the UE has much lower antenna elements number than the AP and use the fixed number of 16 for all frequencies. We assume a log-linear relationship in terms of the beamforming complexity introduced by the increasing number of antennas. The following suitability assessment table can be obtained from this analysis.

Frequency (GHz)	10	28	38	73
Number of transmit antenna	4	32	64	256
Order of BF complexity (O)	$O(2^{10})$	$O(2^{13})$	$O(2^{14})$	$O(2^{16})$
Complexity scaling factor ($\log_2(O)$)	1	8	16	64
Suitability value	10	1.25	0.625	0.1563

Table 6-12 Device complexity KPI analysis – Strand 1

Device complexity KPI – Strand 2 assessment:

The device complexities with regard to extending bandwidths have impacts on multiple points of the transmitter/receiver chains such as the base-band, ADC/DACs (Analog – Digital Converters) Power amplifiers and antenna elements. These hardware components are evolving at a very rapid pace, becoming linear in the higher frequencies and wider bandwidths. Faced with this rapid improvement in a multitude of technologies (even for the same device, e.g., Power amplifiers) it is very difficult to quantify suitability.

We attempted to limit the analysis to a certain component and assess the complexity. In particular we focused on the power amplifier. Considering the different technologies involved and the different costs/ benefits they bring, it is very difficult to carry out an objective analysis. We provide the following reference [PWM+12] as an indication of the different technologies being pursued in the mm-wave spectrum for power amplifiers.

6.4.5 Some Limitations of the Study

The suitability analysis is a very complex task, made complicated by the very wide range of frequencies to cover, the multiple parameters involved and the myriad of interactions amongst the parameters that need be considered. We have made some simplifications in this work and this introduces some limitations.

As the coverage and capacity KPIs were assessed with simulations, some restrictions had to be made to the analysis. This analysis covers only outdoor or outdoor to indoor (in case of capacity KPI) deployments, so it is not applicable to indoor scenarios. Some of the technologies (like WiGig) has now been successfully developed to provide very high capacities for indoor scenarios. Yet these aspects could not be captured in the analysis.

The parameters used themselves do not represent bench mark values for a certain frequency range (e.g., number of antennas). They should be considered as relative values (relative to the reference frequencies used). Thus the parameter values by themselves are not indicative of future system values, but the relative variations of values for each of the KPIs (under the same strand) would carry some significance. It should be emphasized that the variations of the four KPIs should be taken together into account to create meaning of the study, for each strand.

Due to the complexity and time consumption in the multi-cell simulations employed for the coverage and capacity KPI analysis, sometimes we have to work with some coarse step sizes. The 50m step change in cell radius is one example. These coarse changes can have negative impacts in multi- variable analysis as we have done here.

There are mitigating technologies to address some of the issues discussed here. For example although we depicted the number of cells as the key point for coverage, the complexities or costs of deploying smaller cells are much simpler than for Macro cells. We did consider some of the mitigating factors like technology maturity to face some of the problems in mobility. However, for the sake of keeping manageable the complexity of the study, these mitigating technologies could not be considered across board. It is worth noting that the technologies evolve all the time (and particularly at a rapid pace in mm-wave), so some of the issues we took as benchmarks for assessment may lose their significance in due time.

7 Conclusions

In this document, the use cases that will be investigated in the mmMAGIC project are analysed by means of KPIs and requirements. Eight use cases have been described. The selected use cases are not meant to be a comprehensive list, but rather a selection of representative use cases useful to define a technology for extreme Mobile broadband applications. A common list of KPIs have been identified and, for each use case, this list is analysed through defining the specific requirements and describing the gap from the current technology. This analysis naturally identify the most critical KPI(s) that characterize each use case.

In the table below the main challenge for each selected use case has been summarized.

Use Case	Main Challenge (most critical KPIs)
Media on demand	Peak connection density (4000users/km ²)
Cloud services	DL traffic density (up to 750Gbps/km ²), mobility (up to 100km/h)
Dense urban society with distributed crowds	connection density (30000, up to 150000, users/km ²), traffic density (7500Gbps/km ²), bandwidth
Smart offices	DL user data rate (1Gbps), traffic density (15000Gbps/km ²)
Immersive 5G early experience in targeting hot spots	Data rate (x10 average, x20 peak) and cell densification (25 small cells/hotspot area)
50+Mbps everywhere	Coverage
Moving hot spot	mobility (up to 500km/h)
Tactile internet / video augmented robotic control and remote-robot manipulation surgery	availability and reliability (99,999%), low latency (1ms)

Table 7-1 Use cases and main challenges (KPIs)

By analysing it in a critical way, the advantages and the challenges of using mm-waves to address the described KPIs are derived as well as some directions to be followed in order to design a common technology.

In the second part of this deliverable we analysed the mm-wave frequency bands in the range of interest for mmMAGIC (6-100GHz). The frequency range has been subdivided in 3 big chunks, i.e., low (6-30GHz) medium (31-51GHz) and high (71-100GHz), where commonalities can be identified. The current ITU-R spectrum allocation for mobile services has been investigated for the 3 ranges of interest and the available contiguous bands have been identified. The availability of technology components has been then discussed. Such analysis gives an indication of the technology readiness in the frequency ranges for mobile applications. Finally the three frequency ranges are analysed by means of KPIs (named coverage, capacity mobility and device complexity) in order to derive the suitability of mm-wave spectrum for mobile applications. In order to provide some concrete numbers on the suitability, four representative frequencies are studied (i.e., 10, 28, 38 and 73GHz) and a suitability value (on a scale from 0 to 10) is derived. These three analyses combined together lead to a comprehensive view of the frequency range considered by the mmMAGIC project. As output of this study, considering the early stage of the project and of 5G in general, we deliberately decided not drawn conclusions on specific preferred bands but we rather prefer to leave the study focused at the existence/suitability of wider ranges.

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